

OHBM AUSTRALIAN CHAPTER

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Melbourne, Victoria

ABSTRACTS

Organization for
Human Brain Mapping
Advancing Understanding of the Human Brain

OHBM AUSTRALIAN CHAPTER

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Poster No 1

Spectral imprint of structural embedding in effective connectivity

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Neural fluctuations exhibit rich spectral profiles that reflect both local dynamics and structural (or anatomical) embedding. Yet, standard models of resting-state effective connectivity neglect structural embedding and assume uniformity in the timescales of regions' endogenous fluctuations¹. We introduce a chromatic dynamic causal model (DCM) in which structural valency (or degree) modulates the spectral 'colour' of endogenous fluctuations². Specifically, we assume a linear relationship between regional structural valency and the spectral exponent of scale-free auto-spectra. Simulations show this mapping can emerge as a generic consequence of structural embedding under minimal coupling in a nonequilibrium regime. We show chromatic DCM reliably recovers ground-truth parameters across network sizes and noise conditions, outperforming standard spectral DCM. Applied to empirical data, chromatic DCM reveals that valency–exponent mappings vary across a cortical hierarchy, and that its parameters are conserved across a homologous circuit in humans, macaques, marmosets, and mice. These findings advance an account of structure–function coupling that expands the repertoire of mechanisms available for inference in effective connectivity modelling.

Figure. Chromatic DCM links structural embedding to spectral profiles of endogenous fluctuations. Panels illustrate the chromatic DCM framework, which incorporates regional anatomical embedding to constrain the spectral profile of endogenous fluctuations in the context of resting-state fMRI. White–burgundy color gradient reflects spectral color — from white (flat spectra) to pink and red (steeper, low-frequency dominated spectra) — and are used consistently across panels to denote region-specific properties. (a) Structural connectivity (with edge weight reflecting connection strength) is used to compute the normalized valency (degree) of each region, based on the total strength of its anatomical connections. (b) The regional valency shapes the spectral exponent of endogenous fluctuations via a linear mapping. (c) This results in region-specific auto-spectra (power spectral densities) for endogenous fluctuations, with a greater exponent corresponding to redder (steeper) spectra. (d) In the temporal domain, this corresponds to slower fluctuations in regions with higher structural valency. (e) These fluctuations drive neuronal dynamics independent of effective connectivity. (f) Simulated BOLD responses show that (observed) timescales reflect both endogenous fluctuations and effective connectivity. Notation follows Eqs. 1–2.

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Poster No 2

Assessing the significance of brain map associations through effective sample size estimation

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Studying associations between brain maps is complicated by spatial autocorrelation, which violates independence assumption and inflates false positive rates (FPR) in correlation tests. Existing methods mitigate this by generating surrogate maps but suffer drawbacks such as computational cost, missing values on medial wall, and limited generalizability in spatial geometry.

This abstract introduces a surrogate-free method to address this problem, named effective sample size estimation (ESSE). It fits variograms to estimate the covariance structure (i.e., dependence) of data (Fig.A) and computes effective sample size (and effective degrees of freedom) using Dutilleul's modified t. Significance of correlation is then assessed against the theoretical distribution of statistics (Fig.B). To address inflated FPR arising from nonstationary (i.e., spatially varying) autocorrelation discussed in recent work, we further develop nonstationary ESSE (nESSE) to resolve this spatial heterogeneity by fitting variograms for randomly parcellate data (Fig.C).

Simulation studies on spherical meshes (Fig.D) show that ESSE effectively controls FPR at a significance level of 0.05 (Fig.E), performing comparable to established methods (Fig.F). Under nonstationary autocorrelation, nESSE achieves superior FPR control (Fig.G). Our methods generalize across geometries (e.g., partial mesh and volumetric data, Fig.H-K), handle missing values, and scale efficiently (computation time: <1 sec for 1k points, <1 min for 10k points).

In summary, this work develops a method to assess the significance of association between autocorrelated brain maps. It is fast, generalizable across spatial geometry, and effectively works with and without the presence of nonstationary autocorrelation and missing values.

Figure. Assessing the significance of brain map associations through effective sample size estimation. A) Variogram fitting and covariance estimation. Left visualizes an example autocorrelated map. Center compares the empirical and stable-variogram-model fitted variograms for the example data. A variogram describes how (semi-)variance of data (y-axis) change as a function of distance (x-axis), reflecting the autocorrelation of data. Right displays the covariance structure between data points computed based on the fitted variogram. B) Significance p-value as a function of degrees of freedom, for a constant example Pearson correlation coefficient. Without accounting for autocorrelation, the raw degrees of freedom (green asterisk) underrepresent the dependence of data, resulting in small p-value and inflated FPR. Dutilleul's modified t computes effective degrees of freedom (black asterisk) based on estimated covariance structure of data, controlling for the inflation in FPR. Derivation of effective degrees of freedom can be found in Dutilleul et al, 1997. C) Nonstationary ESSE (nESSE) accounts for spatially varying autocorrelation. By randomly parcellating data into spatially continuous parcels (left) and fitting variograms for each parcel (center), nESSE assumes local stationary within parcel and resolves autocorrelation heterogeneity between parcels. With this approach, heterogeneity is reflected between diagonal blocks of covariance matrix (right), where off-diagonal blocks are inferred using nonstationary variogram models based on process convolution (Paciorek and Schervish, 2006). As a result, effective sample size can be computed accounting for the spatial heterogeneity in autocorrelation.

D) Methods are assessed using independently simulated data ranging from no autocorrelation ($I=0$) to strong autocorrelation ($I=50$). E) ESSE (or stationary ESSE, sESSE) and nonstationary ESSE (nESSE) controls FPR well at a significance level of 0.05, for a range of autocorrelation strength ($I=0$ to 50). F) Evaluated with data generated on spherical mesh whose autocorrelation is not spatially varying, the performance of sESSE and nESSE are comparable to established methods, including spin test (st) and eigenstrapping with 50 and 1000 modes (es50 and es 1000). G) nESSE better controls for FPR, relative to sESSE and established methods, when the strengths of autocorrelation spatially vary. Left visualizes example simulated data with heterogenous autocorrelation. We examined three combinations of autocorrelation I (left, 0/50, 10/40, and 20/30). Right visualizes the FPR of different methods at each autocorrelation combination. In brief, sESSE, spin test, and eigenstrapping with 1000 modes failed to control for FPR arising from heterogeneous autocorrelation. nESSE that randomly parcellates data, and eigenstrapping with 50 modes improves FPR, with nESSE based on random parcellation outperforms eigenstrapping with 50 modes. We also show that the performance of nESSE can be improved if ground truth parcellation is provided (nESSEgt), despite this information is often unavailable in empirical data. H) Example autocorrelated data simulated on a partial mesh (a quarter of spherical mesh), ranging from independence ($I=0$) to strong autocorrelation ($I=50$). I) sESSE and nESSE controls FPR for data generated on partial meshes. J) Example autocorrelated data simulated on a cubic volume, ranging from independence ($I=0$) to strong autocorrelation ($I=50$). K) sESSE and nESSE controls FPR for volumetric data.

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Poster No 3

Longitudinal Analysis of the Structural Connectome: Robust Estimation of Fibre Bundle Capacity Differences

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Estimating longitudinal connectivity changes from diffusion MRI remains challenging due to substantial methodological variability in streamline tractography¹. We address this by introducing an unbiased reconstruction framework, enabling robust estimation of longitudinal Fibre Bundle Capacity² (FBC) differences—a connectivity metric sensitive to a bundle's total intraxonal cross-sectional area.

Since axonal connections are established prenatally³, subsequent changes can be postulated to occur within a fixed scaffold. We leverage this constraint by reconstructing only a single tractogram per subject in an unbiased within-subject template. We then use a modified version of SIFT2⁴ to derive session-specific sets of streamline weights: first we derive the session-average densities, which are then symmetrically refined to match session-specific data. From this, we compute edge-wise FBC by summing density weights of streamlines assigned to region pairs (see A). We applied this approach to estimate longitudinal FBC differences in cohorts with biologically expected effects: (1) Scan-Rescan ($n=44$, no change), (2) Developing Children ($n=35$, increases⁵), (3) Temporal Lobe Surgery ($n=52$, decreases⁶). Results were benchmarked against cross-sectional FBC estimation and Fixel-Based Analysis⁷ (FBA).

Cross-sectional FBC estimation produced spurious differences across datasets. In contrast, unbiased FBC estimation revealed the biologically expected patterns: no change in Scan-Rescan, global increases in Developing Children, and ipsilateral decreases post-resection. Unbiased results closely matched FBA findings (see B).

Overall, unbiased connectome reconstruction drastically reduces methodological imprecision, enabling robust quantification of longitudinal connectivity differences.

Figure. A) Cross-sectional vs Unbiased Estimation of Longitudinal Fibre Bundle Capacity (FBC) Differences. Left: Cross-sectional FBC estimation results in variable streamline trajectories across timepoints, with corresponding cross-sectional weights. As such, longitudinal FBC changes are driven by differences in both trajectories and weights. Right: In contrast, unbiased reconstruction fixes streamline trajectories throughout the analysis, ensuring that longitudinal FBC differences are solely driven by changes in their assigned cross-sectional weights. **B) Longitudinal FBC Differences Across Datasets.** Biologically, one would expect no connectivity changes in Scan-Rescan data, global increases in Developing Children, and ipsilateral decreases following Temporal Lobe Surgery. However, cross-sectional FBC estimation produced spurious changes across all three datasets. In contrast, unbiased FBC estimation revealed the expected patterns. These findings were corroborated by Fixel-Based Analysis, which aligned closely with the changes observed using unbiased reconstruction. Abbreviations: FBC = Fibre Bundle Capacity, FDC = Fibre Density and Cross-Section, HCP = Human Connectome Project, WM = White Matter.

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Poster No 4

Echo Planar Time-resolved Imaging for CSF-GM coupling

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Echo planar imaging (EPI) is a workhorse of MRI, widely applied beyond functional MRI to cardiac, spectroscopic, pulmonary, diffusion, and perfusion imaging. Its speed makes it ideal for capturing dynamic brain activity, yet it is highly susceptible to artefacts from field inhomogeneity, susceptibility effects, distortion, and blurring. Multi-shot approaches, which segment the readout over time, mitigate some of these limitations but at the cost of longer acquisition times. The introduction of simultaneous multi-slice (multi-band) imaging more than a decade ago dramatically accelerated acquisitions, enabling sub-second sampling. More recently, the integration of multi-echo sequences and routine field-map acquisitions has further improved robustness for fMRI.

A new approach, Echo Planar Time-resolved Imaging (EPTI), directly addresses the core limitations of conventional EPI by exploiting the strong spatio-temporal correlations in EPI data. EPTI reconstructs distortion-free, multi-echo images without T2/T2* blurring, providing rich temporal and contrast information in a single scan. This enables high-resolution acquisitions that combine spin-echo, gradient-echo, and asymmetric-echo contrasts, making the method particularly powerful for layer-specific fMRI, advanced diffusion imaging, dynamic susceptibility and contrast-enhanced perfusion (DSC/DCE), and quantitative water and multi-parametric mapping.

Here, I demonstrate how EPTI can reveal subtle physiological processes such as cerebrospinal fluid flow-gray matter coupling dynamics, and ways to reduce motion-related artefacts. Together, these advances establish EPTI as a versatile platform for next-generation neuroimaging and quantitative MRI.

Poster No 5

fMRI-Guided Diffusion Models for Visual Brain Decoding

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Decoding visual experiences from human brain activity has long been a central goal in computational neuroscience and computer vision. Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging (fMRI) provides a non-invasive window into neural activity, yet mapping these high-dimensional signals to coherent visual reconstructions remains a formidable challenge. In this work, we propose fMRI-Guided Diffusion Models for Visual Brain Decoding, a novel framework that leverages the generative power of latent diffusion models conditioned directly on fMRI representations. Our approach integrates hierarchical region-of-interest (ROI) features and dynamic functional connectivity to capture both localized and distributed neural patterns. To enhance semantic alignment, we introduce a lightweight multi-head latent attention module that bridges the fMRI latent space with the conditioning pathways of the diffusion model. We validate our method on the Natural Scenes Dataset (NSD), demonstrating that our model reconstructs images with sharper details, higher semantic fidelity, and improved generation consistency compared to existing baselines. These results highlight the potential of diffusion-based brain decoders to advance brain-computer interface research and deepen our understanding of visual representation in the human brain.

Poster No 6

Resistor Capacitor Network Circuit Model for Predicting Network Propagation of Direct Electrical Stimulation

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Background: Brain stimulation evokes activity which can propagate through large-scale networks underlying the structural connectomes. To date, existing models such as the neural mass model and network communication models¹

face challenges in balancing spatial resolution and computational efficiency and lack a biophysical foundation. Here, we introduce a Resistor–Capacitor (RC) circuit model of the human connectome that predicts the direct electrical stimulation signal propagation measured by stereo electroencephalography (SEEG).

Methods: Each brain region was modelled as a capacitor, and white-matter tracts between regions as resistors weighted by structural connectivity and the Euclidean distance. Our SC and ED matrices are based on the group-average connectome from the data using the Human Connectome Project (HCP) and contain 360 cortical regions and 14 subcortical structures.² The maximal current was compared with empirical SEEG amplitude and probability matrices recorded by F-TRACT project.³

Results: The RC model reproduced key propagation patterns observed in SEEG recordings. Predicted maximum current maps showed significant correspondence in the key region pairs (plenty events happen in the select pairs) with empirical probability ($r=0.57$, $p<0.001$) and amplitude ($r=0.44$, $p<0.001$). Also, our model performs well in those indirectly connected nodes (probability ($r = 0.37$, $p<0.001$) and amplitude ($r=0.44$, $p<0.001$)). Our RC model also outperformed several graph-theoretic models.

Conclusions: A simple biophysically grounded RC network can capture large-scale stimulation propagation. This framework provides a mechanistic foundation for predicting electrical stimulation signal propagation and the SEEG responses across the human brain.

Resistor Capacitor network circuit model for predicting network propagation of direct electrical stimulation

Figure:

Figure. (A) The resistor-capacitor circuit is based on the brain’s structural connectome network. The green nodes are the targeting regions we considered, and the orange lines denote the connection between those regions. To analyse the signal propagation through this network, we take the target regions as capacitors and connections as resistors to transfer the brain network into a resistor and capacitor circuit network. Then we applied Kirchhoff’s laws at each node to establish a system of ordinary differential equations shown as the right panel.

(B) Our RC model’s node-wise maximum current map is taken as the prediction results for the comparison with empirical SEEG amplitude and response-probability matrices using Spearman correlations. Other network communication methods’ predictions are also together compared with the empirical data. Bootstrap confidence intervals (2000 samples) and distance-controlled partial correlations were used to assess robustness. Across all stimulation sites, the RC model achieved the strongest or second strongest and significant correspondence with empirical signal propagation in both probability and amplitude comparison.

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Poster No 7

A unified model of cortico-hippocampal interactions through neural field theory

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Functional interactions between cortex and hippocampus play a central role in cognition and are disrupted in major neurological disorders, but the mechanisms underlying coordinated cortico-hippocampal dynamics are poorly understood. We address this challenge using neural field theory, a biophysically-grounded framework for modelling large-scale neural dynamics. We first show how the autonomous activity of cortex and hippocampus emerge from corticothalamic and hippocampo-septal feedback loops, respectively, giving rise to cortical alpha and hippocampal theta rhythms. We next integrate these two systems through topologically and topographically informed coupling between cortex and hippocampus. Weak coupling yields spatially precise correlations between cortical and hippocampal activity, consistent with neurophysiological recordings. Stronger coupling pushes both the cortex and the hippocampus toward criticality, triggering state transitions and mode mixing, such that activity propagates across spatial scales and reorganizes both cortical and hippocampal dynamics. These disruptive, unstable processes also provide an explanation for the frequent involvement of the hippocampus in seizures. This prediction is validated using intracranial electroencephalographic data from human patients with focal onset epilepsy. Together, these results establish a geometrically and biophysically grounded framework that gives a unifying account of large-scale cortico-hippocampal dynamics and provides a physically principled foundation for studying other distributed brain systems.

Figure. Schematic showing the cortico-hippocampal coupling implementation in the Neural Field Theory model. a, The reciprocal coupling between cortex and hippocampus is described by the coupling constants, C_{ch} and C_{hc} .

b, Illustration of the hippocampus-to-cortex coupling, which enables smooth field transfer across surfaces using quasi-conformal mapping.

c–f, Step-by-step depiction of how fields propagate from hippocampus to cortex. Both cortical and hippocampal surfaces are projected onto a shared 2-D domain through quasi-conformal transformations (d and e). The target cortical vertex (f) is located on the 2-D cortical map (e). The corresponding hippocampal region (d) that projects to this cortical vertex is identified using the coupling function, which minimizes the distance between the cortical vertex and hippocampal region in the shared 2-D space. Coupling strength is indicated by a color gradient, with maximum intensity at the center (red) and exponential decay outward.

g–j, Demonstration of field transfer from the hippocampal surface to the cortical surface using this coupling framework. The same approach can also be applied in the reverse direction (cortex to hippocampus) by interchanging the source and target surfaces.

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Poster No 8

Elucidating RNA isoform expression in the 2-day old human prefrontal cortex at single-cell resolution

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Most neuropsychiatric disorders have a developmental origin and many risk genes have been identified¹. Simultaneously, processes like alternative splicing cause most genes to produce multiple mRNA isoforms, some of which are directly linked to neuropsychiatric disorder risk². However, our knowledge of RNA isoforms during human neurodevelopment is limited. Addressing this fundamental knowledge gap would deepen our understanding of how risk gene isoforms can either facilitate healthy brain development or contribute to neuropsychiatric disorders.

As an initial pilot study, we mapped the RNA isoform landscape of 9,988 cells from the pre-frontal cortex of a 2-day-old post-mortem female. After single-nuclei capture (10x Chromium), we performed Oxford Nanopore long-read sequencing and analysed the data using Seurat and our custom bioinformatics pipeline FLAMES³. Using these tools, we assessed isoform expression and diversity across cell types.

We identified 19 major cell types, with three broad groups including excitatory neurons, GABAergic interneurons and non-neuronal cells. We detected 38,825 expressed genes and 141,111 isoforms, including 156 novel isoforms. 38% of isoforms were differentially expressed between cell types, with excitatory neurons showing the greatest diversity. Strikingly, neurodevelopmental disorder (NDD) risk genes typically expressed many mRNA isoforms, e.g. ANK2 and KMT2C.

This is the first single-cell study of RNA isoforms in the post-natal developing human brain. We show extensive isoform diversity, particularly in neuropsychiatric risk genes, and highlight isoforms of interest. Expanding this study across developmental stages will reveal how RNA diversity may contribute to brain health and disease.

Figure. High RNA isoform diversity across genes, particularly neurodevelopmental disorder (NDD) risk genes (red), such as MACF1 (green).

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Poster No 9

Lesions (don't) speak volumes: Language fMRI in the Malformed Cortex

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Malformations of cortical development (MCDs) are an important cause of drug-resistant epilepsy, with lesion resection often the only curative treatment. The involvement of MCD in cognition is unclear, bearing significant implications for surgical planning. We assessed language function across MCD subtypes in 52 patients and 251 controls via nonword-rhyming task (Tailby et al., 2017). T-statistics were generated in SPM12 with peak- (uncorr. <.001) and cluster-level (pFWE <.05) thresholding. Random effects analysis was conducted to determine the language network in controls. BOLD-activated voxels within MCDs were measured with small volume correction. Sixteen patients had bottom-of-sulcus dysplasia (BOSD). One BOSD in left Broca area showed no task activity, despite 91% of controls showing activation within lesion region. An occipital BOSD (Fig 1a) and a left basal temporal BOSD showed activation suggestive of visual processing (pFWE<.05). None of the 17 periventricular nodular heterotopia cases showed activation. Among 19 patients with focal cortical dysplasia (FCD), two had lesions near left Broca area. In both cases, regional activation abutted the lesion margins without extending into the lesion (Fig 1b). One occipital FCD showed activation (pFWE <.05) suggestive of its involvement in the visual aspect of task processing. None of the remaining 29 MCDs showed task activity. Preliminary findings suggest absence of language function within MCDs across the spectrum of corticogenesis. In contrast, MCDs involving unimodal cortex more often show preserved function. Given the focal nature of the MCDs, only a limited number of lesions overlapped with the task network of this study. Further work using a separate paradigm is underway to assess lesions elsewhere in the brain.

Figure 1. Case exemplars where lesion is located within task-relevant regions.

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Poster No 10

Only a matter of time: Developmental heterochronicity captures properties of the human connectome

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The mechanisms which shape the human connectome remain elusive. Models of the connectome have shown that a trade-off between the energetic costs and functional benefits of forming a connection can capture many, but not all, network features. Yet these models overlook key developmental constraints. Spatiotemporal patterns of cortical development are guided by morphogenic gradients during early brain development. Differences in

timing of developmental events across the cortex — cortical heterochronicity — may provide an additional constraint on connectome formation and organisation. We developed a new generative model of the human connectome incorporating cortical heterochronicity. By simulating the propagation of developmental connectivity gradients from focal origins, we constrained network connections to form along a strict spatiotemporal schema. Simulated networks were evaluated on their ability to replicate empirical network properties, including nodal degree, clustering, modularity, and connection length distribution, and were compared to existing trade-off models. Simulated models with dual developmental origins in the hippocampus and frontal cortex best captured empirical network properties (nodal degree: $r=0.50$), outperforming networks generated with one, or three origins. All models substantially outperformed trade-off models in reproducing empirical network features. We created a novel generative network model informed by early cortical development. The best performing models had origins which mirrored known developmental/morphological gradients, with the best two-origin models resembling the dual origins theory of cortical development. Our findings show heterochronicity occurring along spatial gradients combined with wiring-costs constrains cortical connectivity.

Figure. To simulate the propagation of connectivity gradients from focal origins, we first defined a given origin/origins as parcels on the cortex and measured the distance from these points to all others on the cortex. A) Geodesic distances from example origins (red; origins mirrored across hemispheres). B) The normalised geodesic distance corresponds to the point in the model when a region becomes active and can start forming connections. Nodal activation therefore progresses smoothly across the cortical surface, therefore constraining connections to form along a spatiotemporal pattern. C) At each possible timestep T in the range $[0,1]$, the connection weight between two nodes w_{ij} , provided they are both active, is determined by their wiring-cost D_{ij} (exponential decay of shortest white matter distance). The average connection weight across all timesteps is taken to calculate the network W , which is strength thresholded to match the density of the empirical group consensus structural network. D) The 20 best performing models (strongest degree correlation) for one, two, and three origins (compared to trade-off generative network model results), and their primary connectivity gradient correlation (absolute correlation of the empirical and model network first principal components), edge overlap (proportion of connections in the empirical network the model network also captured), clustering similarity (absolute difference between empirical and model network mean clustering), modularity similarity (absolute difference between empirical and model network modularity Q), and edge length similarity (the Kolmogorov–Smirnov statistic between the empirical and model network edge length distributions). E) Proportion of times a region was an origin in the best performing models (one origin: top 20; two/three origins: top 1% models).

Poster No 11

Validity of Resting State fMRI as an Alternative to Language fMRI for Paediatric Language Mapping

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Introduction Accurate language lateralisation during presurgical planning for paediatric epilepsy is critical to minimise postoperative language deficits. Task-based language functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) can be challenging for younger children or patients with cognitive impairments. Resting-state fMRI (rs-fMRI) is a potential alternative, though validation studies have shown varied results. We aimed to determine whether language laterality from rs-fMRI demonstrates concordance with that from task-based fMRI in our clinical cohort. **Methods** This retrospective analysis includes paediatric epilepsy patients (N=37, age 7.69–18.25) who completed task- and rs-fMRI during presurgical workup at the Royal Children's Hospital, 2014–2025. fMRI data were pre-processed with fMRIPREP1. Independent component analysis was performed on rs-fMRI with MELODIC2, and template matching identified language components. Task-based fMRI was processed with FEAT3. To assess concordance, Pearson's correlation was calculated for laterality indices, and Cohen's kappa calculated for categorical lateralisation. **Results and discussion** Preliminary results indicate a moderate correlation ($r = 0.436$) for laterality indices, and poor categorical agreement ($\kappa = 0.099$, $p = .125$) for categorical laterality, between task- and rs-fMRI. This indicates limited validity for individual-level clinical interpretation. **Conclusion** These findings may suggest that while rs-fMRI cannot yet replace task-based methods, it may still provide complementary information for language mapping in paediatric epilepsy. Subsequent analyses will include additional template-matching methods and calculation of overlap between language networks identified via task- and rs-fMRI.

Figure. Overlaid distribution of language network laterality indices calculated from rs-fMRI (blue) and task fMRI (red).

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ADOLESCENCE AND PSYCHIATRIC ILLNESS

Poster No 12

Investigating the role of structural brain development in shaping early life adversity effects on alcohol expectancy formation in alcohol-naïve adolescents

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Purpose: Early life adversity increases alcohol use risk, potentially through shaping cognitive beliefs about alcohol effects. This study examined whether structural brain changes mediate or moderate relationships between early life adversity and alcohol expectancy formation in alcohol-naïve adolescents.

Methods: Using ABCD Study data, we analysed 6,682 alcohol-naïve participants (ages 13-14, 53.2% male). Early adversity was assessed across 13 domains, including ACEs, community violence, safety concerns, and resource scarcity. Alcohol expectancies were measured at 3 years. Changes in grey matter volume in 12 brain regions were analysed as mediators and moderators using SEM with FDR correction.

Results: Multi-adversity youth developed more positive alcohol beliefs and fewer negative concerns. Brain changes did not mediate the effects of adversity on expectancies. However, brain development moderated adversity effects, with deviations from normative trajectories influencing alcohol beliefs differently across adversity contexts. Among multi-adversity youth, preserved cortical volumes were associated with lower positive expectancies ($\beta = -0.0124$, $pFDR = .0164$). Five adversity types showed developmental interactions: physically abused youth with delayed cortical development showed heightened sensitivity to negative consequences ($\beta = 0.2093$ and 0.1368 , $pFDR < .05$).

Conclusions: Brain development moderates rather than mediates the effects of adversity on alcohol expectancies. Individual differences in neurodevelopmental trajectories create differential susceptibility, with brain-expectancy relationships emerging only in youth exposed to adversity, supporting targeted interventions based on both neurodevelopmental timing and environmental risk.

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Poster No 13

Hippocampal Functional Connectivity as a Brain Marker of Early Negative Symptom Development and Functional Outcome in People at Psychosis Risk

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Hippocampal dysfunction has been proposed as a core feature of psychosis and may thus reflect a promising new treatment target. We investigated whether longitudinal changes of hippocampal functional connectivity are associated with early symptom development in people at clinical high risk for psychosis. We analyzed the longitudinal clinical and neuroimaging data from 434 participants of the large-scale multicentric North American Prodrome Longitudinal Study (NAPLS 3) using structural equation modelling. Our results demonstrate that an increase in hippocampal functional connectivity, particularly in homotopic hippocampal connections, is specifically linked to improvements in negative symptoms and global functioning, but not to other symptom domains. This effect was only obtained in people at clinical high risk for psychosis, but not in controls and was restricted to the hippocampus, highlighting both its

pathological relevance and regional specificity. The present finding establish hippocampal functional connectivity as a brain marker of early negative symptom development and functional outcome in people at psychosis risk and thus represent an essential step toward a functional neuroimaging-based treatment target for these clinical domains.

Figure. A) The change of hippocampal functional connectivity over time is plotted on the x-axis, while the change of the six clinical domains is shown on the y-axis. Change scores are displayed as standardized β_z coefficients derived from the single subject regression models. Plots are split by subjects at clinical high risk for psychosis and health controls. The grey dashed lines indicate a β_z of zero. The p values refer to the interaction effects tested in the main statistical analysis. B) The estimates of the effect sizes of the interaction effects from the single indicator regression models are shown. The clinical scores are displayed on the x-axis, while different functional connectivity scores are depicted on the y-axis. The fields are colored if $p_{FDR} < 0.05$. Red indicates a positive association, blue reveals a negative link, and grey fields reflect a non-significant effect. Symp, symptoms; CHR, subjects at clinical high risk for psychosis; HC, healthy controls; VIS, visual network; SMN, somatosensory network, LIM, limbic network; FPN, fronto-parietal network; DMN, default-mode network; SAL, salience network.

Poster No 14

Towards Individualized Care: Affinity Scores Across the Psychosis Continuum

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Psychotic disorders exist along a continuum of symptoms and cognitive impairments with high individual variability, making it difficult to link brain structure with clinical features. To address this, we applied Affinity Scores, an individual-centric framework that quantifies a person's similarity to different psychosis subgroups based on cognitive and clinical data. We analyzed data from 671 participants aged 18 to 60, including healthy controls, individuals at ultra-high risk, first episode psychosis, and schizophrenia. Clinical assessments included global functioning (SOFAS); UHR symptoms (CAARMS), and psychotic symptom severity (PANSS). Cognitive functioning was assessed using WAIS-III for estimating IQ; BACS for verbal memory and working memory, fluency, and processing speed; and CANTAB for spatial working memory, planning, cognitive flexibility, reaction time, and sustained attention. T1-weighted brain scans were conducted on a subset using a Philips 3T whole-body MRI scanner. Images were segmented in FreeSurfer using

Desikan-Killiany atlas and ENIGMA guidelines to estimate regional brain volumes. For each participant and variable, affinity scores to each diagnostic group were computed by analyzing standardized distances within the population. We used linear regression to identify associations between regional brain volumes and affinity scores. We found significant associations between brain volumes and affinity scores across the psychosis continuum. Frontal, temporal, and parietal regions were linked with affinity to healthy controls, while orbitofrontal, fusiform, lingual, and paracentral regions were associated with higher affinity to clinical groups. These findings suggest that Affinity Scores reflect individualized brain-behavior relationships.

Figure. Individual affinity scores of cognitive and clinical variables of each diagnostic group (HC, UHR, FEP, SZC) that are significantly associated with regional brain volumes are mapped using the Desikan-Killiany atlas. Magnitude of p-values are indicated by grading from low (dark) to high (light). Particularly the frontal, temporal, and parietal regions were associated to affinity scores

Poster No 15

Fronto-amygdala and Fronto-hippocampus Functional Connectivity Specialisation in Normal Development and Adversity

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Development of frontolimbic functional connectivity remains to be fully characterised. As frontolimbic circuits are integral to stress regulation (McEwen et al., 2016), elucidating their development is crucial for understanding how adversity relates to developmental deviations (Holz et al., 2020). We aimed to characterise the frontolimbic connectivity development using resting-state functional MRI and test its relationship with adversity. In a developmental cohort (HCP-D; N = 623; ages 8-21), we calculated a specialisation index quantifying whether a voxel's connectivity pattern showed stronger spatial correlation with the canonical fronto-amygdala versus fronto-hippocampus pattern from adults (HCP-YA; N=1,084). We tested this index for associations with development and adversity. Findings were tested for replication (PNC; N = 898; ages 8-23) and extended to a longitudinal early development cohort (BCP, N = 169, ages 0-5). Fronto-amygdala connectivity specialisation increased with age ($r = 0.344$, $P < 0.001$), but fronto-hippocampus specialisation did not ($r = -0.077$, $P = 0.058$). Individuals with greater exposure to adversity had more mature fronto-amygdala connectivity for their age ($r = 0.122$, $P = 0.003$). These findings were replicated in an independent cohort. In early development, fronto-hippocampus specialisation increased with age ($\beta = 0.160$, $P =$

0.002), but fronto-amygdala specialisation did not ($\beta = 0.051, P = 0.314$). In conclusion, fronto-amygdala and fronto-hippocampus connectivity become more spatially specialised over development albeit at different timings. Adversity is linked to advanced maturation of fronto-amygdala specialisation in adolescence. This work provides new insights into the frontolimbic connectivity development and the impact of adversity.

Figure. Frontolimbic specialisation across development and in adversity. A In the HCP-D dataset of childhood and adolescence, fronto-amygdala connectivity pattern, but not fronto-hippocampus, becomes more specialised. Specialisation indicates the degree of which the amygdala or the hippocampus connectivity pattern preferentially resembles its own counterpart of the adults. B Across two cohorts, the fronto-amygdala specialisation is advanced for individuals exposed to more adversity or trauma. C The connectivity difference map depicts in adults where amygdala connectivity is stronger than hippocampus connectivity. HCP-D individuals' fronto-amygdala connectivity pattern maps converge with the connectivity difference map as age and specialisation increase. D Linear mixed effects models show fronto-hippocampus connectivity pattern, but not fronto-amygdala, becoming more specialised in early life.

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Poster No 16

Disentangling white matter alterations across early psychosis and cannabis use disorder: A Fixel-Based Analysis approach

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Schizophrenia is a severe, debilitating disorder that profoundly affects perception, emotion, and cognition, yet neurobiological origins remain poorly understood. White matter alterations consistently reveal disruptions across prefrontal and temporal regions in schizophrenia (Karlsgodt, 2016). However, these findings are widespread and non-specific, particularly early in psychosis onset (EP), a critical period to determine prognosis and disorder trajectory (Moghaddam et al., 2024). While cannabis use is associated with heightened risk of developing schizophrenia (Casadio et al., 2011), it has been often overlooked as a confounding factor when investigating structural connectivity in EP. Here, we use Fixel-Based Analysis (FBA; Raffelt et al., 2015, 2017) to examine white matter microstructural fibre density and cross-sectional effects using diffusion-weighted imaging data. We compare white matter microstructure in EP and

controls, and investigate the distinct and combined effect of comorbid Cannabis Use Disorder (CUD). Data from the Human Connectome Project for Early Psychosis were obtained, including 116 EP patients (25 of which met criteria for comorbid CUD, and 91 did not), and 50 controls. There was significantly lower fibre density in EP patients compared to controls when adjusting for age, sex, and intracranial volume. However, we found no significant difference in fibre density between EP patients with comorbid CUD, and those with no comorbid CUD (FWE-corrected $p > 0.05$). White matter alterations early in psychosis onset seem to be consistent with schizophrenia. While CUD increases psychosis risk, its impact on white matter in EP needs to be further elucidated in future longitudinal studies that track the progression from EP to chronic schizophrenia.

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Poster No 17

Role of oestradiol and progesterone variability across a month in brain structure and mental health in adolescent females

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Background Adolescent females are especially vulnerable to mental health symptoms (MHS) and emotional dysregulation (ER). Puberty introduces oestradiol (E2) and progesterone (P4) cycling, with high variability before and soon after menarche, similar to other hormonal transitions. In adults, variability during postpartum and perimenopause has been linked to brain and mental health changes, but its role in adolescence is unclear. We examined whether within-individual E2 and P4 variability relates to brain structure and MHS/ER, to better understand psychopathology risk in adolescent females

Methods Participants (N = 147 females, 11–16 years) were from the Puberty and NeuroDevelopment in Adolescents (PANDA) study. E2/P4 variability was indexed as the within-participant SD of monthly hormone levels (see Figure 1). Depressive, anxiety, and ER symptoms were self-reported; externalising symptoms were parent-reported. Cortical thickness, surface area, and subcortical volumes were estimated in FreeSurfer v7.3.2. Regression and mediation models tested associations between E2/P4 variability, brain structure, and mental health/ER, controlling for age, menarche and demographics

Results Greater P4 variability was linked to smaller left thalamus volume (Cohen's $d = -0.26$, $pFDR = 0.031$). Higher E2 variability predicted fewer anxiety ($d = -0.170$, $pFDR = 0.043$), depressive symptoms ($d = -0.179$, $pFDR = 0.036$) and lower ER ($d = -0.179$, $pFDR = 0.036$). Effects were stronger pre-menarche

Conclusion P4 variability may influence thalamic development, while E2 variability relates to reduced MHS/ER, particularly before menarche. Hormone variability in adolescence may shape brain–behaviour links differently from adult transitions, underscoring the value of longitudinal research in larger samples

Figure. PANDA study design. Each individual collects a weekly saliva sample and the positive and negative affect schedule (PANAS) for a month. E2 and P4 were assayed using saliva samples. MRI was done at the final collection, and behavioural measures were collected one week before MRI.

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Poster No 18

Genetic and Network-Based Constraints on Gray Matter Volume Changes in Psychosis

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Schizophrenia is associated with stereotypical changes in regional grey matter volumes (GMV), however, the mechanisms shaping these changes remain unclear. Recent work suggests that reductions in GMV spread through white matter tracts between connected regions. Here, we extend existing models by incorporating interactions between brain networks and genetic risk factors.

Empirical GMV changes were assessed using voxel-based morphometry analyses on MRI data from 17 scan sites. Structural connectivity was derived from diffusion MRI data. Gene expression profiles were provided by the Allen Human Brain Atlas. Our disease model employed an agent-based Susceptible-Infected-Removed (SIR) model, simulating disease progression based on gene expression within regions and connectivity between regions.

Simulated pathological processes and subsequent atrophy were tested across all combinations of potential risk and clearance genes. The resulting atrophy maps were compared with empirical data to determine peak correlations, reaching a maximum correlation of $r=0.71$ (Fig 1A, B). Simulated atrophy from gene pairs with high model fit significantly outperformed null models (Fig 1C). Gene enrichment analysis on highly performing genes revealed significant enrichment in terms associated with synaptic signalling and protein translation.

Our model integrates genomic and connectomic data to simulate GMV changes in psychotic illnesses. Our results indicate that disease processes, constrained by genomic expression, accumulate locally and propagate along the connectome to shape the distribution of GMV changes in psychosis. We identify altered neurotransmission and cytoplasmic translation as key biological processes associated with GMV changes in schizophrenia.

Figure. A. Top: Surface projection of empirical GMV changes in psychosis. Bottom: SIR model simulated GMV changes replicate spatial patterns of GMV changes. B. Model fit per region at peak correlation ($r = 0.715$). C. SIR model performance (red) outperforms both spatial (left) and rewired (right) null models (blue box-and-whiskers, $p < 0.0001$).

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Poster No 19

Investigating the fractional occupancy of brain states during an emotionally salient video in psychosis using hidden Markov modelling – preregistration

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Schizophrenia is a disorder that affects multiple domains (thought, perception, emotion). Emotional disturbances encompass negative symptoms such as flat affect and anhedonia, alongside deficits in emotional expression, perception and recognition. Tapping into emotional processing with robust ecologically valid stimuli holds promise for characterising brain network dynamics and individual differences in psychosis.

In this study we acquired fMRI data of 80 invited participants (40 with transdiagnostic psychosis) who viewed emotional videos. We will utilise a hidden Markov model (HMM) to identify underlying brain states driven by the stimuli. We will then quantify how much time is spent in each brain state (fractional occupancy (FO)). We will link these brain states and their transitions to emotional properties of the movie. We will further validate these brain states and networks with brain maps obtained through the metanalytical open access Neurosynth database. We will compare the FO of the different brain states for our experimental vs control groups using Bayesian t-tests. We hypothesise that there will be a significant difference in the fractional occupancy of different brain states between the two groups.

The negative symptoms of schizophrenia, characterised by impaired emotional processing, form the majority of burden of disease but remain poorly understood with no effective treatments. Studying differences in occupied brain states during an ecologically valid emotional stimulus offers novel insights into the disease. These findings will shed light on new targets for ongoing investigation and treatment formulation.

Analysis Plan for full project can be found here: <https://osf.io/3sgba/>

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Poster No 20

Constricted Affect, Distress, and Interoception

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A main challenge in psychiatry research is identifying the transition from subclinical to clinically relevant symptom expression. Research suggests that symptom-related distress may influence how individuals process their symptoms in at-risk populations. We are investigating this relationship in an ongoing study, involving participants from the general population who report high levels of constricted affect (CA). CA is associated with psychosis-spectrum disorders and defined as an attenuation of emotional expression. Participants completed novel social-affective tasks and self-report measures assessing symptoms of psychosis and associated distress (CAPE-42) and perception of their bodily signals (MAIA-2; interoceptive awareness). We hypothesise that self-reported high distress regarding one's symptoms is related to lower heart rate (HR) in response to social-affective stimuli and lower scores on interoceptive awareness measures. Preliminary analyses show anecdotal evidence in favour of a negative relationship between negative symptom distress and HR when participants see a face coupled with a negative auditory stimulus (N=23; BF10=1.08), and evidence for a negative relationship with interoceptive awareness (MAIA body listening; BF10 =5.09 and MAIA self-regulation; BF10=2.58). These preliminary results suggest that the brain-body connection of individuals with CA may be weakened. However, more data is needed to provide clear evidence for these effects.

Poster No 21

Probing the Craving Neurocircuitry in Cannabis Use Disorder Using Real-Time fMRI Neurofeedback

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Background: Cannabis Use Disorder (CUD) affects approximately 50 million individuals globally and is linked to a range of negative psychosocial and health outcomes, which have been ascribed (in part) to hyperactivity in the craving neurocircuitry including the anterior cingulate cortex (ACC) amongst other regions. However, how craving-related function changes in real time remains unexamined, leaving prominent neurobiological theories of addiction untested in CUD. We investigated whether real-time functional MRI neurofeedback (fMRI-NF) can be used to volitionally engage the craving neurocircuitry in CUD, with a focus on the ACC.

Methods: Ten individuals with moderate-to-severe CUD were tested at the 7 Tesla MRI at the Melbourne Brain Centre Imaging Unit (MBCIU). Participants completed: (i) a "localiser" cue-reactivity fMRI task to identify which part of the

ACC (i.e., ROI) was most consistently engaged at the individual level; (ii) two fMRI neurofeedback runs to up-regulate ROI activity via increasing the height of a “craving bar” displayed via a screen in the scanner, showing the % signal change participants achieved in the ROI. Group-level data was analysed using whole-brain and ROI-based general linear models.

Results: ROI analysis results showed that the ACC activity decreased during up-regulation ($t = -6.57, p < .05$), comparing to neutral blocks. Whole-brain analysis results (Upregulation > Neutral) showed significant deactivation across frontal ($t = 9.76, p < .05$) and parietal ($t = 11.50, p < .05$) regions. Conclusion: The findings suggest previously unrecognised plasticity in craving-related networks, differing from prominent neuroscientific theories of addiction, and need to be validated in larger samples.

Figure. Whole-Brain Activation Maps for Upregulation > Neutral and Neutral > Upregulation Contrasts. Axial slices displaying whole-brain results from combined Run 1 and Run 2. Red clusters indicate regions with significantly greater activation during upregulation (Up > Neutral), including midbrain, brainstem, and white matter regions. Blue clusters reflect regions with greater activation during neutral blocks (Neutral > Up), showing cortical and subcortical areas such as the insula, angular gyrus, and superior frontal cortex. Maps are FDR-corrected at $p < .05$ and overlaid on a standard MNI template. The color bar represents t-values. Warm colours (right scale) for upregulation-related activation, cool colors (left scale) for Neutral > Up activity.

Poster No 22

A closed-loop fMRI-neurofeedback system for probing the addiction neurocircuitry during craving, using ultrahigh field MRI

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Background: Functional magnetic resonance imaging-based neurofeedback (fMRI-NF) is a brain-training technique to enable individuals to self-regulate brain activity. We aimed to evaluate learning (i.e., increase in beta coefficients from a region-of-interest [ROI], the anterior cingulate cortex [ACC]) and region-specificity (i.e., ACC versus a control region) of the feedback signal, using a personalized closed-loop fMRI-NF system setup in an ultrahigh-field (i.e., 7T) fMRI scanner.

Methods: 7 healthy adults with a mean age of 30.8 years underwent four 8-minute runs of fMRI-NFB, to regulate their craving or motivational arousal. The system integrated: (i) the MRI scanner, (ii) a computer including a real-time processing software (Turbo-BrainVoyager) to measure changes in the ROI activity — % signal change in ACC and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF); (iii) a stim PC running a custom script that denoised the feedback signal by regressing out CSF-related activity, applied weighted sliding window smoothing, and converted the resulting values into real-time visual feedback — a thermometer designed in MATLAB — to present to participants. Feedback signal was modelled as a regressor in the general linear model using offline parametric modulation analysis, with beta values representing the regional specification level (RSL; i.e., the degree to which BOLD fluctuations in a region were explained by the feedback signal). Region specificity was determined by comparing RSL across the ACC, motor cortex, and CSF.

Results: RSL increased across runs ($\Delta = 5.6$, $d = 0.47$), and was higher in the ACC than control ROIs ($p = 0.043$), confirming region specificity. Conclusion: The findings indicate that the fMRI-NF setup enables ROI learning and ROI-specific modulation in real time.

Figure. Regional specification level for ROIs Across Neurofeedback Runs. Bar graphs illustrating the regional specification level extracted from four pre-defined ROIs across all four neurofeedback runs. Separate graphs are presented for "Up regulation Runs" (left) and "Down regulation Runs" (right). The ROIs include ACC (red), Right Hand Knob (green), and CSF Confound (blue).

Poster No 23

Amygdala volume and distress symptomology in cannabis use disorder

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Cannabis use disorder (CUD) is associated with elevated psychological distress, partly attributed to disruptions in brain reinforcement processes and emotion regulation pathways. However, amygdala alterations remain inconsistent, and the role of distress in CUD-related morphology is poorly understood. This study investigated the relationship between CUD severity, distress, and amygdala volume in regular cannabis users. Structural T1w/T2w scans were used to compare amygdala volumes between non-using participants ($n=32$) and cannabis users meeting DSM-5-TR criteria for CUD ($n=80$), stratified by CUD severity (mild, moderate, severe). Subsequent hierarchical structural equation modelling investigated the role of distress (comprising depressive, negative affective, anxiety, perceived stress symptomology) on the relationship between CUD and amygdala volume. A quadratic trend in whole amygdala volume was observed across groups ($p=.01$), with the severe CUD group displaying smaller volumes than the moderate group ($p=.03$). There were no overall group differences in volume. Greater CUD severity was associated with smaller whole and left lateral amygdala volumes (all $p<.04$). Distress did not mediate this relationship, but led to loss of the direct effect between CUD and right whole amygdala volume. Smaller amygdala volumes in severe CUD may reflect cumulative effects of prolonged stress and reinforcement-related neural disruptions associated with addiction

processes. The loss of a direct effect after accounting for distress suggests a suppressor effect, whereby distress masks or accounts for variance in amygdala morphology otherwise attributed to CUD severity. Longitudinal studies may clarify time-sensitive effects of CUD and associated patterns of distress on amygdala morphology.

Poster No 24

EEG derived dynamic brain states during TMS therapy for depression

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Background: Transcranial magnetic stimulation (TMS) effectively treats symptoms of refractory major depressive disorder (MDD). However, the neurophysiological mechanisms underlying treatment response remain unknown. This longitudinal study aims to close this knowledge gap by tracking likely changes in dynamic brain state while participants undergo personalized TMS treatment for MDD.

Methods: MDD patients (n=40) underwent TMS treatment (4 to 6 weeks) with weekly subjective symptom assessments. Resting-state eyes-closed electroencephalography (EEG) was recorded longitudinally at three treatment timepoints, with pre/post-TMS recordings at each session (total of 6 recordings per patient). We used time-delay embedded hidden Markov modelling (TDE-HMM, Vidaurre et al., 2018) to define dynamic brain states. We analysed state-specific fractional occupancies, power, coherence, and transition probabilities across treatment progression.

Results: Approximately half of the patients showed a clinical response (< 50% symptom reduction) to personalized TMS. TDE-HMM revealed distinct brain states characterised by power and coherence patterns. Baseline self-report symptom scores predicted fractional occupancy in a frontal default mode state during the first session, with more time spent in this state predicting greater depression severity. Fractional occupancy patterns were stable across sessions.

Conclusions: Dynamic brain states are linked to depression severity at baseline. Our results suggest that dynamic brain states may track TMS induced symptom improvements during treatment.

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Poster No 25

The Effectiveness of Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation in Suicidality: An Updated Systematic Review

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Suicidal thoughts and behaviors (STB) have a substantial global burden, with over 14 million individuals attempting suicide annually. Existing therapies do not adequately reduce STB risk. Repetitive transcranial magnetic stimulation (rTMS) is an approved, non-invasive, low-risk treatment for several psychiatric disorders and may provide much-

needed treatment options for STB. Given the recent proliferation of studies investigating rTMS' effect on STB, an updated review of the literature is warranted.

Method: A PRISMA-guided systematic review was conducted to evaluate the efficacy of rTMS in reducing STB. Studies assessing STB outcomes following rTMS to treat psychiatric disorders, either as monotherapy or adjunctive treatment, were included. Forty-five studies were identified (N=3515).

Results: Studies generally applied rTMS to treat primary psychiatric disorders, particularly treatment-resistant depression, with change in suicidality evaluated as a secondary outcome. rTMS protocols differed across studies. Most studies targeted the left dorsolateral prefrontal cortex (dlPFC), although significant improvements to STB were also reported with rTMS targeting the visual cortex, right and bilateral dlPFC. High frequency rTMS and intermittent theta burst stimulation (iTBS) protocols were superior in reducing STB compared to other stimulation protocols, with studies reporting 40-100% STB treatment response rates. Adverse events were mostly mild and transient.

Conclusion: rTMS appears to be a safe and effective treatment option for STB, particularly when rTMS or iTBS is applied to the left dlPFC. Mechanistically informed randomized controlled trials specifically designed to evaluate rTMS' treatment effects on STB are needed to validate this promising treatment approach.

Poster No 26

Locus coeruleus signal intensity in fibromyalgia relative to healthy controls

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Background: Fibromyalgia is a chronic pain condition without an established etiology. However, noradrenergic dysfunction is a possible mechanism to explain the constellation of symptoms associated with fibromyalgia. Noradrenaline synthesis in the locus coeruleus (LC) results in a paramagnetic by-product, neuromelanin. Recently, a magnetic resonance imaging sequence sensitive to neuromelanin has been used to assay LC signal intensity, as a proxy for noradrenergic system function. In this study, we used MR imaging to investigate the noradrenergic-locus coeruleus system in participants with fibromyalgia and healthy controls.

Methods: Forty-six participants with fibromyalgia and 41 healthy controls were recruited for a cross-sectional characterization of LC signal intensity at 3T, quantified from a 2D gradient echo acquisition. Participants completed the Revised Fibromyalgia Impact Questionnaire, as well as measures of anxiety, depression, sleep and the THINC-it cognitive battery.

Results: An independent groups t-test revealed no differences in LC signal intensity between participants with fibromyalgia and healthy controls. In participants with fibromyalgia, partial correlations accounting for age showed no association between LC signal intensity and fibromyalgia history, fibromyalgia symptom severity, anxiety, depression, insomnia or cognitive performance.

Conclusions: LC signal intensity as measured by MR did not distinguish participants with fibromyalgia and healthy controls, nor was it associated core fibromyalgia pain symptoms or associated symptoms. Dynamic measures of noradrenergic function may be required to understand noradrenergic contributions to fibromyalgia.

Figure. Raincloud plots showing locus coeruleus signal (LC) signal following harmonization in the fibromyalgia (shown in green) and healthy control (shown in orange) groups. Scatterplots represent individual values from participants, with boxplots showing the interquartile range, and the whiskers extending to the most extreme value within 1.5 times the interquartile range from the hinge.

Poster No 27

Characterising the Relationship Between Brain Morphology and Psychopathology in Traumatic Brain Injury Using Normative Modelling

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Moderate-severe traumatic brain injury (TBI) is often associated with structural brain changes and persistent psychopathology. Brain morphology typically shows weak associations with traditional diagnostic categories, potentially due to the limitations of categorical nosologies. Here, we apply a novel transdiagnostic framework — The Hierarchical Taxonomy of Psychopathology Following TBI (HiTOP-TBI), and normative modelling, to examine broad and specific associations between brain morphology and psychopathology. Thirty-nine individuals with moderate-severe TBI (Age M=50.22, 74% male) completed a psychological assessment battery and T1-weighted MRI. Cortical thickness and subcortical volume were extracted using FreeSurfer, with manual lesion correction. We examined associations between HiTOP-TBI dimensions (one general factor, two broad internalizing and externalizing spectra, seven lower-order factors) and neuroanatomical deviations derived from normative modelling using linear regression, with false discovery rate correction. Participants endorsed elevated Somatic Symptoms, Peculiarity, Anger, and Ordering compared to norms. There were 59% participants with a focal lesion, predominantly in the temporal (33%) and frontal (28%) regions. We expect that some morphometric features will show broad associations with higher-order psychopathology dimensions, while specific regional associations at the lower-order level will correspond to distinct psychopathological features. Findings would support the utility of HiTOP-TBI in elucidating structural brain deviations linked to both broad and specific psychopathology. Understanding these distinctions is important for advancing neuroimaging research and in clinical formulation of MRI findings for those with psychopathology and TBI.

Poster No 28

Structural brain imaging biomarkers for predicting seizure recurrence after first unprovoked seizure

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Objectives: Predicting seizure recurrence following a first unprovoked seizure (FUS) remains a clinical challenge, especially when routine clinical MRI and EEG lack abnormalities diagnostic of epilepsy. We incorporated structural MRI biomarkers into prediction models for seizure recurrence at 12 months and identified predictive brain structural features.

Methods: We analysed a retrospective, multi-centre cohort of 197 adult patients with FUS; n=83 seizure recurrence, n=114 no seizure recurrence at 12 months, all had normal or non-diagnostic MRI/EEG findings. Morphometric features were extracted from clinical 3T T1-weighted MRI using FreeSurfer. Machine learning models were trained on combined imaging and clinical features, using nested cross-validation for model selection. Performance was compared to a logistic regression model on clinical features only.

Results: The best performing model, a support vector machine trained on combination of imaging and clinical features, achieved an AUC of 0.65 (95% CI: 0.57–0.73), significantly better than chance (p=0.01 compared to AUC 0.5). The logistic regression model trained on clinical features alone yielded an AUC of 0.57 (95% CI: 0.49–0.65), not different to chance (p=0.28). Comparison between these two models was not statistically significant (p=0.11). Inter-

hemispheric asymmetry of subcortical and cortical grey matter volumes and regional gyral curvatures, particularly in fronto-parietal and limbic regions, were predictive features.

Significance: Quantitative structural MRI biomarkers add predictive value for machine learning models of seizure recurrence after FUS. Grey matter cortical and subcortical asymmetries, most likely developmental, are associated with seizure recurrence and precede the diagnosis of epilepsy.

Figure 1: (a) Nested cross validation model performance, showing the highest AUC-ROC of each model algorithm type, with 95% confidence intervals in square parenthesis, demonstrating that the Support Vector Machine was the model selected based on highest AUC-ROC. (b) Final cross validated performance of SVM model, as compared to the final cross validated performance of the clinical factor-only model. Abbreviations: SVM – support vector machine, RF – random forest, LASSO - Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator, XGB – Extreme Gradient Boosting, Clin – clinical factor-only model, AUC-

(c) Feature importance of cortical and subcortical regions

Colours represent a scaled Shapley value*, obtained from taking the feature with the maximum absolute Shapley value (an estimated contribution of each feature to the final classification), of all features belonging to either (i, ii) cortical or (iii) subcortical atlas region. **Abbreviations:** dc – diencephalon

(i) Left lateral, left medial, caudal view

(ii) Right lateral, right medial, ventral view

(iii) Left and Right subcortical regions

Poster No 29

Comparison of Automated vs. Manual Glioblastoma Segmentation Using Multiparametric MRI

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Introduction: Glioblastoma is a highly aggressive brain tumour with poor prognosis. Accurate segmentation of tumour regions is vital for treatment planning and prognostication. This study evaluated an automated segmentation pipeline using multiparametric clinical MRI scans, compared to manual segmentation.

Methods: Clinical MRI data from ten glioblastoma patients was accessed from John Hunter Hospital. Preoperative scans included T1-weighted, contrast-enhanced T1-weighted, T2-weighted, and T2-FLAIR. These were used to generate tumour masks (oedema, contrast enhancing tumour, necrosis) via automated and manual segmentation. Volumetric analysis was performed using an in-house FSL pipeline. Manual segmentation was conducted on Siemens Syngo under expert guidance (MF) for comparison of enhancing and necrotic regions.

Results: 90% of patients were male, with an average age of 63.6yrs (± 13.3). Volumetric analysis showed strong agreement with manual segmentation. Average similarity for the combined (contrast enhancing + necrotic) region was 89.41% (± 6.51 ; $p=0.68$). Similarities for enhancing and necrotic regions were 87.40% (± 7.04 ; $p=0.70$; $r=0.967$) and 91.43% (± 5.22 ; $p=0.85$; $r=0.963$), respectively.

Conclusions: The automated segmentation method showed reliable performance in glioblastoma using multiparametric MRI. This approach may support clinical practice by enabling accurate tumour volume measurements in a time-efficient manner. Further validation with a larger dataset is warranted.

Poster No 30

Magnetoencephalic investigation of neural correlates of capsaicin-induced urge to cough

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MEG was used to investigate the neural correlates of a perceived urge to cough (UTC) evoked by 24-second capsaicin or saline inhalation (18 inhalations per scan) in healthy volunteers ($n = 15$).

UTC was reported by the participant at the end of each inhalation using a button box to indicate a score between 0 and 10. Source modelling was carried out using a linearly constrained minimum variance beamformer, and results are reported for both scalar and vector versions. Significant effects were identified using maximum statistics to provide strong control of the family-wise error rate.

Contrasts between measured oscillatory power (neural activity index, NAI) showed significant suppression of activation in the capsaicin condition relative to saline in alpha (8-13Hz) and beta (13-30Hz) bands in somatosensory regions, primarily precentral, postcentral and supramarginal gyri, corresponding to similar suppression in mid-range frequencies reported in a study investigating neural responses to pain¹.

Significant positive correlations (Kendall tau) between UTC ratings and NAI in corresponding trials were found in delta (2-4Hz) in the nucleus tractus solitarius, a brainstem region known to be involved in the cough reflex², as well as thalamus; and also in insula and frontal pole in gamma (30-80Hz) and high gamma (80-120Hz) bands. These regions were identified in previous fMRI studies into UTC, providing additional evidence that whole head MEG can be used to image deep structures in the brain.

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Poster No 31

Investigating the Spatiotemporal Profile of Consciousness using Dynamic Causal Modelling

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Two major theories of consciousness make distinct predictions about the spatiotemporal profile of neural activity that elicits conscious perception. Information Integration Theory (IIT) posits that sustained posterior activity in content-specific networks generates consciousness, whereas Global Neuronal Workspace Theory (GNWT) proposes that a phasic, ignition of a frontoparietal network is necessary for consciousness. Using magnetoencephalography data from the COGITATE consortium, we applied dynamic causal modelling (DCM) to test brain connectivity patterns proposed by either theory. First, source reconstruction was performed to determine peak voxels driven by faces at stimulus onset within six regions of interest - bilateral primary visual cortices, fusiform gyri, and prefrontal cortices. DCMs comprising these regions were fully connected at each level and connectivity parameters were estimated at the group-level via parametric empirical Bayes. To evaluate the temporal profile of connectivity, we modelled evoked responses to task-irrelevant faces in an expanding time window increasing in steps of 0.1s, starting from onset up to 0.6s post-stimulus offset. Preliminary results from a discovery cohort (n=48) simultaneously challenged and provided partial support for both theories. Specifically, we found sustained activity in posterior connections that was sustained beyond the stimulus offset. Additionally, we saw phasic increases in feedback connectivity at both stimulus onset and offset in some (but not all) of the key connections. While these preliminary findings do not clearly align with either theory, final results will include a validation cohort of 52 additional participants to test the reproducibility of these findings.

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Poster No 32

Bidirectional modulatory influences of aversive and appetitive stimuli on habenula function and effective connectivity

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The habenula (Hb) is a key region for encoding negative reward prediction error – a phenomenon that encourages behavioural adaptation in response to unexpected negative outcomes (Proulx et al., 2014). Although animal studies have revealed that the Hb is bidirectionally modulated by aversive and appetitive stimuli (Groos & Helmchen, 2024), there have been few direct human neuroimaging studies that have addressed the ‘bidirectional modulation’ hypothesis. Here, we leverage two experimental tasks and ultra-high field 7T fMRI to characterise habenula response to aversive and appetitive stimuli. Across the reversal learning and prediction uncertainty tasks, we use dynamic causal modelling to assess habenula directed causal connectivity in a sample of healthy adults (n = 47 and n = 43, respectively). The presentation of aversive and appetitive stimuli reliably bidirectionally modulates habenula connectivity to the ventral tegmental area and dorsal raphe nucleus, with the former exhibiting a negative modulatory effect and the latter a positive modulatory effect. We further present task-specific modulatory differences for subcortical to cortical (dorsal anterior cingulate cortex and medial prefrontal cortex) connections. Our study evidences the underlying nuances involved in the encoding of reward prediction error via the habenula and its extended circuitry. This work will be important for understanding how habenula hyperactivation in major depressive disorder is mitigated by ketamine antidepressant treatment and the subsequent impact at circuitry-level.

Figure. Task elicited effective connectivity. Comparison of the elicited modulatory effective connectivity across the reversal learning (n = 47) and motion prediction (n = 43) tasks. Each bar represents the Bayesian model-averaged (BMA) connectivity strengths as measured in Hz for each modulated connection thresholded at a posterior probability (Pp) of >.95. The reversal learning task is presented in grey with the motion prediction task overlaid in pink. Whiskers represent the 95% confidence interval (CI) as derived from the posterior covariance matrix (spm_plot_ci). The graph is split into the modulatory effects of aversive feedback and appetitive feedback, aversive feedback refers to unexpected punishment and incorrect feedback presentation, whereas appetitive feedback refers to expected reward and correct feedback presentation for reversal learning and motion prediction tasks, respectively. Hb, habenula; VTA, ventral tegmental area; DRN, dorsal raphe nucleus; dACC, dorsal anterior cingulate cortex; mPFC, medial prefrontal cortex.

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Poster No 33

Genetic architecture of MRI-derived cervical spinal cord morphology reveals sensory-motor axis and systemic disease biomarkers

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The spinal cord is critical to motor, sensory, and autonomic function, and is increasingly implicated in neurological disease and human health, yet its genetic architecture remains largely unexplored. We present the first large-scale phenotyping of the upper cervical spinal cord (C1–C3) using brain magnetic resonance imaging from over 40,000 UK Biobank participants¹. We implemented an optimized deep learning–based pipeline designed for accurate vertebral labeling and robust segmentation of the upper cervical cord². We extracted shape metrics including cross-sectional area, anteroposterior and right–left diameters, and eccentricity. We identified 179 independent genome-wide

significant loci, with cervical spinal cord morphology showing moderate to high SNP-based heritability (0.16–0.42). We also uncovered sex-specific genetic signals, suggesting biological sex differences in spinal cord development and morphology. Beyond locus discovery, we systematically examined phenotypic and genetic correlations between cervical spinal cord structure and brainstem and subcortical regions, revealing strong shared associations with regions involved in sensory and motor pathways. Leveraging health-related outcomes, spinal cord structure showed widespread associations with neurological, metabolic, and systemic conditions, including multiple sclerosis, neuropathies, diabetes, and attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder. Together, these findings establish the cervical spinal cord as a genetically informative and health relevant structure, offering new opportunities to study its role in disease mechanisms and human health.

Figure. Genome-wide associations of cervical spinal cord shape metrics. (a) An overview of the spinal cord image processing pipeline using T1-weighted brain MRI from the UKB. Following spinal cord segmentation and vertebral labelling of C1 to C3, spinal cord shape metrics including the mean CSA, eccentricity, AP and RL diameters were derived. (b) Overview of the GWAS study design for spinal cord shape metrics. We conducted GWAS of 12 MRI-derived spinal cord shape phenotypes, including CSA, eccentricity, AP and RL diameters at cervical levels C1 to C3. Quality control included sample and genotype filtering, with imputation using the TOPMed reference panel. Discovery analyses were performed in individuals of European (EUR) ancestry, including sex-stratified GWAS, followed by post-GWAS analyses. Replication was carried out in C/SA, EAS, and AFR cohorts. Reproduced by kind permission of UK Biobank[©].

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- Enigma-SC. github.com/art2mri/Enigma-SC.

Poster No 34

Brain-heart coupling shapes large scale brain dynamics

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Functional brain networks reconfigure to support adaptive behaviour, balancing integration and segregation. These dynamics are influenced by neuromodulatory arousal, reflected in heart rate (HR) fluctuations. We leverage intracranial EEG (iEEG), functional MRI (fMRI), and HR recordings during emotional movie viewing to probe neurocardiac

contributions to large-scale network dynamics. Network dynamics using high-frequency iEEG activity (60–140 Hz), an established marker of neuronal firing, reveals that greater network integration tracks elevated HR, while segregation aligns with lower HR. However, we observe an inverted relationship between HR and network dynamics in a separate fMRI data utilising the same movie, and replicate this in another independent fMRI dataset. Biophysical modelling of BOLD from iEEG reproduces the iEEG-HR findings, suggesting neurovascular transformation may obscure neural-cardiac links in fMRI. These results link large-scale network dynamics to physiological arousal through HR driven adrenergic-cholinergic neuromodulation and highlight the complex interplay between neural activity, autonomic regulation, and haemodynamics.

Figure. Hypothesis and schema for analytical approach. (A) The Locus Coeruleus, a noradrenergic brainstem nucleus, has diffuse projections throughout the cortex and subcortex, facilitating the integration of brain networks. In contrast, the Basal Nucleus (of Meynert), a cholinergic brainstem nucleus, exhibits sparse projections to localized networks, promoting segregation in brain networks. While in-situ neurotransmitter dynamics are challenging to measure directly, heart rate (HR)—controlled by the adrenergic-cholinergic balance—serves as a proxy for assessing this balance. (B) To investigate our hypothesis, we utilized intracranial EEG (iEEG) data, which offers millisecond temporal resolution at a meso-network spatial level, and functional MRI, which provides macroscale global brain coverage. (C) A 20-minute emotional movie was used to probe dynamic graph properties, with integration and segregation metrics extracted from windowed data (sliding window analyses for fMRI data) to generate their respective time series. Mean HR was computed for each corresponding time window to establish a link with the integration and segregation time series.

Poster No 35

If the doors of self were cleansed – effective connectivity of ego dissolution

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Ego dissolution (ED) offers a unique lens for examining the neural basis of self processing. While prior neuroimaging studies have examined ED using functional connectivity (Stoliker et al., 2022), they have not addressed effective connectivity, namely the directed causal influences between brain regions. This study aims to characterize effective connectivity differences between individuals reporting high and low ED, thereby advancing mechanistic understanding of self-disintegration under psychedelics. Data are drawn from the PsiConnect trial (Novelli et al.,

2024). Spectral Dynamic Causal Modelling (spDCM), a Bayesian method that infers effective connectivity by fitting a biophysical generative model to the cross-spectral density of BOLD signals (Novelli et al., 2025), was applied to resting-state fMRI data. The model included five regions implicated in functional accounts of ED: parahippocampal cortex (PHC), hippocampus (HP), retrosplenial cortex (RSC), posterior cingulate cortex (PCC), and medial prefrontal cortex (mPFC) (Lebedev et al., 2015; Carhart-Harris et al., 2016). We hypothesize that high ED will be associated with a breakdown in directed connectivity between the PHC and RSC, leading to reduced top-down influence from the PCC and mPFC to the HP. These patterns are expected to correlate with MEQ Mystical subscale scores, whereas low-ED individuals will show stronger PHC–RSC connectivity. The anticipated findings support an account of ED as a sequential decoupling within the autobiographical memory system—first between PHC and RSC, then between higher-order hubs and the HP—disrupting contextual binding and the integration of sensory input with higher cognitive representations and ultimately contributing to the dissolution of self-boundaries.

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Poster No 36

Context-Dependent Brain and Behaviour Dynamics under Psilocybin

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Background: Psilocybin, a serotonergic psychedelic, induces profound alterations in consciousness often experienced as meaningful and coherent. While these effects may underpin clinical potential, psychedelic brain dynamics have frequently been characterised as desynchronisation (Muthukumaraswamy et al., 2013; Siegel et al., 2021). We advance this view by examining psilocybin's effects across experimental contexts using the largest psychedelic neuroimaging dataset to date.

Methods: In an open-label study at Monash Biomedical Imaging, fMRI and EEG were recorded in 60 healthy adults (18–58 years) during multiecho eyes-closed rest, meditation, music, and eyes-open movie viewing scans, before and after 19 mg psilocybin. Mindset measures and validated psychedelic questionnaires were acquired. Alongside conventional analyses and dynamic causal modeling, we used CEBRA, a contrastive-learning method for joint neural-behavioural embeddings (Schneider et al., 2023), and TAVRNN, a Temporal Attention-enhanced Variational Graph Recurrent Neural Network for modelling time-varying connectivity (Khajehnejad et al., 2025), to characterise brain dynamics across conditions.

Results: Our analyses revealed a structured organisation in brain activity, dependent on experiential context and the intensity of subjective psychedelic effects, and a shift in eyes-open versus eyes-closed states under psilocybin.

Conclusions: Our multimodal approach combining fMRI, EEG, and machine learning provides a comprehensive and revised account of psilocybin's acute effects on brain activity, offering new insight into the neurobiological mechanisms underlying transformative psychedelic experiences and methods for predicting clinically relevant outcomes.

Figure. Psilocybin reorganises brain activity along low-dimensional trajectories that scale with subjective effects.

a) Using CEBRA—a machine learning method that decodes neural activity over time using contrastive learning—for each participant, we mapped the time series of all 332 brain parcels at each time point into a 3D space, resulting in a trajectory spanning the entire duration of the four tasks. The pink segment represents rest, while the blue, green, and yellow segments represent the meditation, music, and movie conditions, respectively.

b) Network embeddings (CEBRA-derived trajectories) for a participant (PC201), who reported no subjective effect onset during the MRI session on the day of psilocybin administration, showing similarity to their baseline (no-psilocybin) scan. This suggests that neural embedding changes depend on the alignment of subjective states within the imaging time frame.

c) For each participant's CEBRA trajectory, a Support Vector Machine (SVM) was used to classify the correct condition label for each time point. The left panel shows the Pearson correlation between the classification accuracy and acute psilocybin subjective effects including 11 Dimensions of Altered States of Consciousness (11D ASC) and Mystical Experiences Questionnaire (MEQ30) scores. Colours indicate subgroups: Blue = positively felt (euphoric) self- and boundary effects; Orange = sensory-hallucinogenic effects; Red = negatively felt (dysphoric) associative effects; Purple = other (combination) effects. * indicates statistical significance. The right panel displays the classification accuracy for each subject, compared to the chance level of 0.25, across the four conditions. Subjects are ordered in ascending order based on their MEQ scores.

d) A Temporal Attention-enhanced Variational Graph Recurrent Neural Network (TAVRNN) was used to map the 332 ROIs into a 2D space during each condition. The top row shows the average 2D embedding of participants with highest MEQ scores (80–100), while the bottom row shows that of participants with lowest MEQ scores (0–20). Each node corresponds to one ROI and nodes are colour-coded based on their brain network. The axes represent abstract latent dimensions learned by the model and do not correspond to physical spatial coordinates.

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Poster No 37

Brain network dynamics supporting positively biased updating of self-beliefs

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Beliefs guide cognition and behavior, with people typically updating their beliefs more in response to favourable versus unfavourable information. The neural mechanisms underlying this positivity bias, particularly in relation to enduring beliefs about oneself, remain to be fully understood. Here, we had 48 healthy adults complete a novel self-belief updating paradigm during 7-Tesla functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) to test effective connectivity between default mode network (DMN) and salience network (SN) regions that have been linked to self-referential cognition and belief updating. Bayesian modeling broadly confirmed positivity bias in self attributes. Dynamic causal modeling revealed excitatory effect from the posterior cingulate cortex (PCC) to the left anterior insular-opercular cortex (AI-O) during self-belief updating, which was decreased as update magnitude increased. We also observed stronger bilateral AI-O excitation and within-network inhibitory effects from ventral anterior cingulate cortex (VACC) to dorsomedial prefrontal cortex (DMPFC) and PCC associated with increased update magnitude, suggestive of 'maintenance' versus 'change-oriented' updating behavior. The excitatory effect from VACC to DMPFC during favourable updating further indicated how valence coding drove belief updating. Together, these findings establish how large-scale dynamic brain network interactions enable humans to maintain optimistic yet adaptable self-concepts.

Poster No 38

Distinct brain mechanisms support trust violations, belief integration, and bias in human-AI teams

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QUT

This study provides an integrated electrophysiological and behavioral account of the neuro-cognitive markers underlying trust evolution during human interaction with artificial intelligence (AI). Trust is essential for effective collaboration and plays a key role in realizing the benefits of human-AI teaming in information-rich and decision-critical contexts. Using electroencephalography (EEG), we identified neural signatures of dynamic shifts in human trust during a face classification task involving an AI agent. Viewing the AI's classification elicited an N2-P3a-P3b event-related potential (ERP) complex that was sensitive to agreement with the participant's own judgment and modulated by individual response biases. In addition, we observed a centro-parietal positivity (CPP) prior to participants' responses, and found that ongoing EEG activity in this time window co-varied with subsequent changes in AI trust ratings. These neural effects showed substantial individual variability, indicating the use of diverse metacognitive strategies. Together, these findings suggest that trust in AI is shaped by internal confidence signals and evaluative processing of feedback.

Figure. A. Reliability ratings (in %) across all blocks of experiment of participant 1 (one rating after each block, including the practice block). B. Difference in reliability ratings between blocks (e.g., reliability rating of block 1 - rating of practice block) for participant 1. Positive differences are colored green, negative differences purple. C. Overview of differences in reliability ratings between blocks for all participants. The first row depicts results of participant 1 and is identical to the data shown in panel (B) presented with a color map. The color map quantifies the difference in reliability ratings between blocks. D. ANOVA outcome for covariance between changes in reliability ratings and ERP amplitude over participants. Results are shown as heat map indicating significant F-values in red over channels and time points. Topological distributions are presented at -520 ms (before AI classification). In the topoplots electrodes belonging to significant clusters are marked white; non-significant electrodes are marked black; results are corrected with spatiotemporal clustering at an alpha level of 5%.

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Poster No 39

How do topologically complex connections support brain function?

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Background Most cortico-cortical connections follow the Exponential Distance Rule (EDR), whereby connection probability decays exponentially with distance¹. A small subset deviates from this rule, forming topologically complex connections, or EDR exceptions, most of which are long-range². Though sparse, these connections are hypothesized to coordinate distributed neural activity, yet their functional contributions remain poorly understood.

Methods We used a whole-brain neural mass model to test how EDR exceptions influence attractor dynamics³. The human structural connectome was derived from diffusion MRI tractography of the HCP dataset, and EDR exceptions were defined as edges exceeding predicted weights under the EDR fit. We simulated dynamics with and without these exceptions and quantified attractor properties: number, transition energy (average and maximum), and repertoire diversity.

Results Including EDR exceptions reduced average and maximum transition energies compared to models without them. Their presence also expanded the attractor repertoire, producing a richer and more diverse landscape. These effects highlight the disproportionate role of few spatially atypical connections in shaping large-scale dynamics.

Conclusions EDR exceptions enhance efficiency and diversity of neural dynamics by lowering energetic barriers and broadening attractor repertoires. Though rare, they appear critical for supporting the flexibility and diversity of brain activity, with implications for understanding structural constraints on cognition and behavior.

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Poster No 40

Towards multiscale dynamic theories of cognition in human neuroimaging

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Technological advances and computational models have been pushing resting-state fMRI towards multiscale, dynamic explanations of neural activity. Task fMRI studies instead still rely on descriptive, single-scale frameworks that limit our understanding of how cognition emerges from neural activity. Here, we bring a new computational perspective to task fMRI and re-examine a core principle of human cognition: cognitive control. We ask whether the three constituents of cognitive control popularised in psychology (inhibition, switching, working memory) emerge as shared or distinct neural patterns from a system that is dynamic and multiscale. Our approach integrates methods from statistical physics (Iterative Coarse Graining) and routine neuroimaging (Multiplication of Temporal Derivatives, General Linear Models) into a unified pipeline, allowing us to identify how task structure (within & across tasks) drives the dynamic reconfiguration of cortical and subcortical regions into spatially coarser coordinated modules. We first test our approach *in silico* using simulations with prespecified modular structure and different task designs. We show our approach's ability to isolate task-modulated functional connectivity, surpassing traditional methods. We next apply our method to task fMRI data from 60 healthy young adults completing three tasks tapping into cognitive control's core constructs (Go/No-Go, Task Switch, N-back). Results reveal that these constructs share common neural patterns at the regional level but progressively diverge at coarser scales, implying that their neural implementation is scale dependent. Our study introduces and highlights the power of a multiscale, dynamic approach for task fMRI and demonstrates its utility in advancing theories of cognitive control.

Figure. (a) Methodological workflow: ICG – MTD – GLM. (b) Simulations showing how MTD isolates task correlations. (c) Empirical results: cortical network & subcortical/cerebellar betas x ICG level x task

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Poster No 41

Deep Learning Based Classification of MI-EEG Signal for BCI Application

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BCIs are emerging as transformative technologies for people suffering from severe motor impairments. Among multiple brain activity paradigms, MI-EEG signals stands out due to its non-invasive nature, capability to provide accurate and reliable neural markers of intended motor task and affordability. However, classification of MI-EEG signals remains challenging because of inherent limitations such as low SNR, high inter- and intra-subject variability, and non-stationarity of signals, which restrict the performance of traditional ML models relying heavily on handcrafted features. Our work addresses these challenges by developing a DL based pipeline for multi-class classification of MI-EEG signals using both self-recorded data from the OpenBCI Ultracortex Mark IV headset and the publicly available PhysioNet MI-EEG dataset. Primary MI-EEG dataset was generated by employing a cue based experimental paradigm drawing four distinct motor imagery tasks; left hand, right hand, both hands, and both legs. Post-data acquisition refinement was done to address issues of packet-based transmission errors, DC offsets, and electrode impedance variability, ensuring reliable dataset preparation. Standard preprocessing steps were used for downstream analysis. EEGNet was employed to efficiently capture temporal and spatial features of MI-EEG signals for the classification task. The model achieved test accuracy of 89.59% on the primary dataset and 73.31% on the PhysioNet MI-EEG dataset, demonstrating strong performance even with lower (16) number of electrodes. These findings demonstrates the feasibility of deploying affordable and portable EEG systems in real-world application, thereby allowing low income nations other avenues besides the traditional approaches for neurorehabilitation.

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Poster No 42

Characterising whole-brain responses to single-pulse perturbations of in silico neural masses

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Neural mass models (NMMs) are mathematical descriptions of neural activity primarily used in validating theories of healthy and pathological brain function at multiple scales and predicting long-term behaviour of neural systems¹. NMMs are particularly useful for studying neural communication, especially at large scales, where a direct probe of neural mechanisms is practically challenging. Typically, NMMs are configured to maximise similarity to empirical dynamical and statistical relationships. However, with the limited availability of suitable empirical communication benchmarks, the large-scale stimulus propagation characteristics of NMMs have remained largely unexplored. An understanding on this front is essential to accurately predict the network effects of perturbations and further enable us to utilise NMMs as a virtual testing ground for neurostimulation paradigms. In this work, we take a step towards addressing this question, by evaluating the ability of two popular NMMs that differ in their biophysical complexity – Stuart-Landau and Jansen-Rit, to accurately predict stimulus propagation across the human structural connectome. We benchmark model performance against whole-brain direct electrical stimulus-response measurements from

the Functional TRACTography dataset (F-TRACT)². We find that while both models show a significant association to empirical response probabilities and amplitudes, interestingly, the relationship does not hold when the physical distance between the regions are regressed out. This indicates propagation accuracy only in the source's neighbourhood. Our initial findings suggest that modifying the NMMs to precisely represent non-local (polysynaptic/multi-hop) interactions is a crucial step towards refining their communication features.

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Poster No 43

Urgency cues compress subjective time and shift decision policy: VR-EEG evidence with hierarchical DDM

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Urgency pervades everyday environments but its neural and computational bases remain underspecified. We tested how urgency cues reshape time perception and decision policy using a virtual-reality (VR) interval reproduction task combined with EEG and hierarchical drift-diffusion modeling (HDDM). Thirty adults completed blocks with urgency (countdowns/visual pressure) versus control cues while reproducing target intervals. Behaviorally, urgency produced a robust compression of subjective time (~30% underestimation) and a pronounced speed-accuracy trade-off. Time-frequency analyses revealed increased frontal theta and reduced sensorimotor beta during urgent trials, indexing elevated control demands and motor readiness; ERPs (CNV, P3) were attenuated, consistent with disrupted temporal accumulation. HDDM implicated lower boundary separation and increased drift under urgency, indicating hastier commitments with biased evidence integration. Together, convergent behavioral, neural, and computational signatures show that urgency compresses perceived duration and reconfigures decision policy toward premature action. Findings align with predictive processing accounts in which priors favor early responses under time pressure, and they suggest mechanisms for impulsivity in high-urgency human-computer interactions and clinical phenotypes. Methodologically, our VR-EEG-HDDM pipeline provides a reproducible approach for linking neural dynamics to latent decision parameters in naturalistic timing tasks.

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AGING AND NEURODEGENERATION

Poster No 44

Structure-metabolism coupling in healthy aging: a multimodal brain network analysis

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Investigating how the brain's anatomical wiring shapes its dynamic activity is essential for understanding cognition, ageing, and various psychiatric and neurodegenerative disorders. Evidence from functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) indicates that brain activity is constrained by underlying white matter structure. Compared to fMRI, functional [18F]-fluorodeoxyglucose positron emission tomography (fPET), a recent advance, enables more direct and quantitative measurement of dynamic brain activity through glucose metabolism. Yet, the extent to which metabolic activity is influenced by the brain structure has not been established. In this study, we examined the structure-metabolism coupling using simultaneous PET-MR in 85 healthy adults, divided into younger (n = 40, mean age 27.9

years, range 20-42) and older ($n = 45$, mean age 75.7 years, range 66-89) groups. Diffusion MRI and resting-state fPET data were preprocessed with standard pipelines, and brain regions were defined according to the Schaefer 100-node atlas. Preliminary analysis demonstrated a significant correlation between structural and metabolic connectivity across individuals (Spearman $\rho = 0.34$, $p < .001$). Moreover, structural-metabolic coupling is significantly weaker in older compared to younger participants ($t = 3.11$, $p = .0025$). These findings provide initial evidence that white matter structure constrains metabolic activity, and that the structure-metabolism coupling diminishes with age. Ongoing analyses will extend these findings to examine more detailed spatial and network-level patterns.

Poster No 45

Metastable coupling between cerebrospinal fluid flow and global brain activity in older adults

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The coupling between cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) flow and global blood oxygen level-dependent (gBOLD) signals has been suggested to reflect coordinated neural and vascular clearance mechanisms. Most prior work has relied on a single cross-correlation function to assess CSF-gBOLD coupling strength^{1,2}. Yet a recent study has shown that ventricle-brain BOLD dynamics can manifest in multiple modes, pointing to richer temporal structure³. Here, we analysed resting-state fMRI from 67 participants (aged 51–80, 47 females) part of the Australian Dementia Network study. The cohort was a composite of healthy older adults ($n = 60$) and those living with MCI ($n = 6$) and Alzheimer's dementia ($n = 1$). The gBOLD signal was extracted from a grey matter mask. CSF signal was derived from the fourth-lowest slice to obtain high sensitivity to the CSF inflow effect. Both signals were z-normalised and bandpass filtered. Using windowed cross-correlation of CSF and gBOLD signals (Fig. 1A) combined with a hidden semi-Markov model⁴, we identified five recurrent coupling states (Fig. 1B), each with distinct lag and correlation profiles (Fig. 1C). State 4 and 5, characterised by strong CSF-gBOLD coupling, were significantly less prevalent in females than in males (Fig. 1D). These results demonstrate that CSF-gBOLD interactions are not static but organised into transient states with distinct physiological signatures. By showing that CSF-gBOLD states are influenced by gender, our findings highlight potential pathways through which clearance-related dynamics could contribute to dementia risk.

Figure. States of CSF–gBOLD coupling. (A) Windowed cross-correlation (WCC) between cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) inflow and gBOLD signals in three representative participants. Each panel shows correlation coefficients across scanning time and lag, with colour indicating the correlation strength. (B) A hidden semi-Markov model applied to the WCC columns identified five recurrent coupling states, with colours indicating which state was expressed at each timepoint for individual participants. (C) Mean cross-correlation profiles for each state, showing distinct signatures of coupling strength and lag. Some states are characterised by strong coupling (e.g. State 4 and 5), while others show weaker or more diffuse interactions. (D) Group-level analyses of state occupancy fractions revealed statistically significant gender differences in States 4 and 5 (* $p < 0.05$, p corrected for multiple comparison).

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Poster No 46

Age Sensitive Hippocampal Functional Connectivity: New Insights from 3D CNNs and Saliency Mapping

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Hippocampus is affected in normal aging but understanding its functional connectivity (FC) change is limited. Seed-based FC enables voxel-wise mapping of hippocampal synchrony with cortical regions, offering insight into its organization across the lifespan. Using fMRI data from HCP young¹ and aging cohorts², we derived bilateral hippocampal seed-based FC maps (Fig. 1e) and fed them to 3D convolutional neural network (CNN, Fig. 1a) for age prediction. The model was pretrained on young adults, fine-tuned on the aging cohort, and evaluated using mean absolute error (MAE). Interpretability was achieved with LayerCAM³ saliency maps (Fig. 1b&c), compared against FC maps and simple regression results. We also examined sex differences and the distinct roles of anterior and posterior hippocampal FC in age prediction through t-tests. CNN models achieved similar performance (Fig. 1g) with MAE = 7.30/7.14/7.31 using whole/anterior/posterior hippocampal FC, respectively. Saliency maps (Fig. 1d), highlighted precuneus, cuneus, PCC, PHC, left SPL, and right STS, as key predictors, consistent with regions known to change with age. The saliency map also differs from input FC maps (Fig. 1e) and the conventional regression results (Fig. 1f),

showing strong ability of CNN in capturing nonlinear patterns from voxel-wise FC maps. Sex-specific effects (fig. 1d) underscored the model sensitivity. Investigating hippocampal subregions further revealed distinct aging trajectories (Fig. 1h), highlighting models' sensitivity. Our interpretable CNN framework moves beyond linear approaches, uncovering complex hippocampal–cortical FC patterns linked to aging. These findings offer novel insights into the neural mechanisms of healthy aging and informing strategies to support cognitive health.

Figure. (a) 3D CNN architecture used for age prediction using seed-based FC. The model stacks five convolution blocks, each containing one convolutional layer (Conv3D), one batch normalization layer (BatchNorm3D), a ReLU activation, and a max-pooling layer (MaxPool3D). Two types of convolution blocks with different kernel size are used in the convolutional layer. One of them uses the kernel of size 3x3x3 and the other one uses a 5x5x5 kernel. After convolutional blocks, a dropout layer followed by one fully connected layer is used to output the predicted age. (b) LayerCAM on the natural 2D image for object localization. (c) LayerCAM adapted to 3D for age prediction task. The saliency map of stage 1 corresponds to the saliency map generated based on the first convolutional layer. The fused saliency map is the final heatmap after combining the maps from all 5 stages. (d) The one on top we have the average saliency map for age prediction using whole hippocampal cortical FC on the aging subjects. The higher saliency values (brighter colour) mean a higher contribution to the age prediction model. On bottom, we show the FDR corrected t-test's z-scores mapped to the brain surface, showing the differences between the saliency maps for male (M) and female (F) subjects. Z-scores were thresholded by 1.645. Hotter regions with higher z-scores indicate more significant differences. (e) The one on top is the average hippocampal FC of aging subjects. Positive values (red/yellow) are correlations, and negative (blue) are anticorrelations. On bottom we have the overlapping map between the mean saliency map in (d) and FC map. The saliency map and average FC map are thresholded to show the regions with the highest 20% values (highest absolute value for FC). (f) The one on top is the thresholded z-scores derived from Bonferroni-corrected p-values obtained through linear regression analysis, showing regions with significant linear relationship between their hippocampal FC and chronological age. Z-scores are thresholded at 1.96. The one on bottom is the overlapping map between the mean saliency map in (d)

and z-score map. The saliency map is thresholded to show the regions with the highest 20% values. (g) The predicted age versus the chronological age for the aging subjects. The black line shows the identity line (i.e. perfect prediction). Age prediction made by the models using the whole hippocampal FC is shown on top. On the bottom, we show the model performance using anterior (left) and posterior (right) hippocampal FC. (h) The corrected t-tests' z-score mapped to the brain surface, showing the differences between the saliency maps based on anterior (A) and posterior (P) hippocampal FC. Z-scores were thresholded by 1.645. Hotter regions with higher z-scores indicate more significant differences.

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Poster No 47

The Impact of Exercise on Brain Structure, Pain, and Cognition in Individuals with Hip Osteoarthritis

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Osteoarthritis (OA) is a chronic degenerative condition characterised by pain and stiffness, leading to reduced wellbeing and economic burden (Vitaloni et al., 2019). Beyond musculoskeletal pathology, OA is also associated with structural and functional brain alterations in regions implicated in pain and cognition (Hall et al., 2023). Exercise is widely recommended for OA management (Goh et al., 2019); however, its potential to induce structural brain changes remains underexplored. This study examined whether a 12-week exercise intervention could alter brain structure, reduce pain, and improve cognition in individuals with hip OA. It was hypothesised that it would increase grey matter volume and cortical thickness in the right prefrontal cortex, insula, and hippocampus, which would be associated with reduced pain and enhanced cognition. Twenty-nine participants in Melbourne, Australia, completed an exercise program, self-reported pain measures, and the Montreal Cognitive Assessment (Memory Index Score). Paired-sample t-tests indicated significant reductions in pain and improvements in memory, as well as increases in right insula and frontal pole cortical thickness, and right frontal pole grey matter volume. However, these effects did not survive correction for multiple comparisons. Correlations showed no associations between structural changes and clinical improvements. Findings suggest exercise produces meaningful symptomatic benefits for people with hip OA, even without detectable brain changes. Null imaging results may reflect modest sample size, short intervention duration, or limited sensitivity of measures (Hvid et al., 2021; O'Driscoll & Shaikh, 2017). Further research is needed to clarify whether clinical improvements are accompanied by neuroplastic changes.

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Poster No 48

Enlarged perivascular spaces as a biomarker of disease in progressive supranuclear palsy

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Objectives: Perivascular spaces, a component of the glymphatic system are involved in clearing waste from the extracellular space in the brain. Enlarged PVS (ePVS) are indicative of glymphatic impairment and are visible on structural MRI, allowing for quantification. This study aimed to investigate the potential use of ePVS as a biomarker of disease in PSP Richardson syndrome (PSP-RS).

Methods: Using an automated algorithm developed in house we segmented ePVS on MRIs in 15 PSP-RS subjects. The density of ePVS in the white matter (WM) and basal ganglia (BG) were associated with the PSP rating scale (PSPRS), disease duration, CSF total tau (t-tau), glial fibrillary acidic protein (GFAP) and neurofilament light chain (NfL) using Spearman's correlation.

Results: WM ePVS correlated strongly with CSF NfL ($r=0.59$, $p<0.04$) and t-tau ($r=0.66$, $p<0.02$), however there was a negative correlation with disease duration ($r=-0.69$, $p<0.005$) (Fig 1). The correlations with t-tau and disease duration survived correction for multiple comparisons. Disease duration was also found to have a moderate negative trend with NfL ($r=-0.3$, $p=0.31$). No associations with BG ePVS or PSPRS scores were observed.

Conclusions: This study suggests that WM, but not BG ePVS may have potential as a biomarker of disease in PSP. The positive association between ePVS and NfL may indicate that ePVS may also be a measure of neurodegeneration. The negative relationship between both NfL and ePVS with disease duration may suggest that these measures are indicative of more aggressive disease. Further research should investigate ePVS in a longitudinal cohort to determine if ePVS impact progression rates in patients with PSP.

Figure. Relationships between PVS density, CSF biomarkers and disease duration

Poster No 49

Mapping Regional Brain Aging in Huntington's Disease Using Structural MRI and Machine Learning

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Huntington's disease (HD) is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder. Models of brain biological age have shown evidence of accelerated aging relative to chronological age, but they typically rely on a single whole-brain measure. While studies in other neurodegenerative diseases suggest region-specific brain age models can provide deeper insights, this approach remains underexplored in HD. Such regional models could benefit clinical trials, which depend on sensitive biomarkers to monitor therapeutic effects.

This study aimed to characterise region-specific patterns of brain aging across HD-ISS stages and evaluate their associations with cognitive, motor, and functional scores.

We employed machine learning to train brain age models on structural MRI data from 2,369 controls. These models were applied to 531 persons with HD. Associations between regional brain age gap, HD-ISS stages, and clinical scores were assessed.

Whole-brain aging increased progressively at HD-ISS stages 2 and 3. Region-specific analyses revealed the dominance of subcortical, temporal, and parietal aging trajectories, which exhibited significant stage-wise increases in brain age gap. A higher brain age gap in these regions was associated with declines in cognitive, motor, and functional performance. In contrast, insular and frontal regions showed flatter patterns and no significant associations with clinical measures.

This study highlights distinct region-specific components of brain aging in HD. Regional analysis provides deeper insights into HD progression and could be employed as a sensitive biomarker for monitoring therapeutic effects in clinical trials. Future work should explore these findings in younger cohorts and investigate network-specific aging with multimodal imaging.

Figure. Stage-wise comparison for regional age gaps in cortical areas.

Poster No 50

Effects of computerised cognitive training on functional brain networks in Huntington's disease: a pilot study

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Background: Huntington's disease (HD) is a rare, genetically inherited neurodegenerative disease that affects fronto-striatal brain networks, leading to decline in processing speed and executive functions (1,2). Computerised cognitive training (CCT) is a potential cognitive intervention that has not yet been thoroughly investigated in HD (3). We conducted a randomised pilot trial of CCT in pre-manifest and early-stage HD and examined effects on fronto-striatal networks during processing speed and cognitive flexibility tasks.

Method: 16 participants were randomised to either multi-domain CCT (2 x 60 min sessions per week for 12 weeks; n = 6) or lifestyle education (n = 10). Participants completed MRI scanning at baseline and follow-up, involving structural MRI and functional MRI during processing speed and cognitive flexibility tasks. We assessed changes in task performance and task-related functional activity and connectivity of fronto-striatal regions, in the CCT group versus the lifestyle education group.

Results: Groups were matched on demographic and clinical variables, and total grey matter volumes. One CCT group participant was excluded from analyses. Across the study period, there was maintained task switching accuracy and improved processing speed in the CCT group, compared to the lifestyle education group. However, there were no significant effects on fronto-striatal activity or connectivity during tasks.

Conclusions: CCT benefited cognitive performance without simultaneous effects on functional activity and connectivity of fronto-striatal regions. This contrasts findings of increased grey matter volumes in the same cohort and may reflect greater sensitivity of structural outcomes (4). Larger trials are required to further explore neural mechanisms of CCT.

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Poster No 51

Depression reduces structurally informed network flexibility in premanifest Huntington's disease

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How structural connectivity constrains effective connectivity in depression and neurodegeneration remains poorly understood. We applied novel structural connectivity-informed spectral dynamic causal modelling (DCM) to examine how anatomy shapes directed inter-regional influences in premanifest Huntington's disease with and without depression history.

Using a novel hierarchical empirical Bayes framework(1), we analysed fMRI data from 98 premanifest participants across default mode network and striatum. Participants were grouped by depression history, and depression severity on both the BDI-II and HADS-D was used. Leave-one-out cross-validation tested predictive validity.

Model evidence favoured structurally informed over uninformed approaches. Having a history of depression was associated with reduced baseline variability in effective connectivity, with tight regularization of near-zero-valued structural connections toward zero effective connectivity values. Effects converged on striatal self-connectivity and hippocampal-striatal pathways, with distinct patterns emerging between groups. Notably, clinically elevated depression revealed differential connectivity signatures, with right caudate self-connectivity showing positive correlations with clinical cut-offs for all participants. Specific connections including DMN-to-striatum (BDI: $p = .002$; HADS-D: $p = .001$), right hippocampus-to-left caudate (BDI: $p < .001$; HADS-D: $p = .002$), and left caudate-to-left putamen (BDI: $p < .001$; HADS-D: $p = .003$) predicted depression severity scores.

These findings link reduced network flexibility to depression vulnerability in premanifest neurodegeneration, providing a mechanistic bridge between anatomical constraints, effective connectivity alterations, and depression phenotype.

Figure. Structural connectivity constrains effective connectivity for HDGECs with depression history | (a) Schematic representation of default mode network (medial prefrontal cortex [MPFC], posterior cingulate [PCC], and bilateral hippocampi [HPC_L, HPC_R] and striatal (bilateral caudate [CAUL, CAUR] and putamen [PUL, PUR]) structural connectivity projected on axial, sagittal, and coronal planes. Line thickness indicates structural connection strength. (b) Model evidence-weighted prior-variance transformations show how structural connectivity scales prior variance of effective connectivity across all HDGECs. Shading denotes standard error envelope. (c) Depression history modulates the baseline variance (a) of effective connectivity, with HDGECs showing depression history (orange) versus those without (blue). $P(\Delta\alpha \neq 0)$ and $P(\Delta\beta \neq 0)$ indicate posterior probabilities (P) that group differences exist for α (variance) and β (slope) parameters, respectively. (d) Log-Bayes factors showing increased group-level model evidence. Red triangle indicates log-Bayes factor threshold of 3 (considered significant). Group-level mean effective connectivity patterns derived from hierarchical models incorporating depression status as a covariate: (e) HDGECs without depression history and (g). HDGECs with depression history. Red indicates excitatory connections and blue indicates inhibitory connections. (f) Between-group differences in effective connectivity comparing HDGECs with depression history versus those without, derived from covariate models. Purple indicates increasing connectivity while brown indicates decreasing connectivity. Off-diagonal entries represent directed inter-regional influences (Hz). Positive evidence set at 75% posterior probability throughout.

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Poster No 52

Poor Diet and Cardiometabolic Risk Jointly Relate to Altered Functional Brain Organisation in Healthy Older Adults

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Healthy dietary habits and lower cardiometabolic risk both support healthy brain ageing, yet their joint association with functional brain organisation remains unclear. We analysed cross-sectional data from 175 cognitively intact older adults (60–70 y) in the ACTIVate study¹. Diet scores were derived with principal component analysis of food frequency data, leading to three diet scores: plant-dominant, meat-dominant, Western-style. Cardiometabolic markers included blood pressure (diastolic and systolic), waist circumference, triglycerides, HDL-cholesterol, and glucose. Resting-state fMRI was preprocessed with fMRIPrep and parcellated using the 17-network Schaefer-400 atlas². Partial Least Squares correlation was used to identify patterns of covariation between lifestyle variables (3 dietary patterns, 6 cardiometabolic markers) and functional connectivity (79,800 edges) using 1,000 permutation tests. One significant latent variable (LV) emerged ($p=.018$), explaining 59% of shared variance (other LVs were non-significant). The lifestyle loadings (strongest to weakest) included higher waist, blood pressure, glucose, and meat-dominant/Western diets, alongside lower HDL and plant diet scores. For the imaging LV, the strongest positive loadings were between-network connectivity (notably in Default-Visual, Default-Somatomotor, and Control-Default) and the strongest negative loadings were within-network connectivity, especially within Default and Visual networks (see Figure 1). The imaging LV connectivity pattern strongly correlated with lower a segregation index ($r=-0.92$, $p<.001$)³. These findings suggest that, in older adults, sub-optimal diet quality and elevated cardiometabolic risk are jointly associated with reduced functional brain segregation.

Figure. Chord Diagrams of Top 10 BSR Network Connections from Partial Least Squares (PLS) Analysis. Functional connectivity among 400 Schaefer parcels was summarised at the 17-network level. For clarity, each panel shows the top 10 network pairs ranked by maximum BSR; within each pair the edge with the largest BSR is plotted (only considering $BSR \geq 2.0$; $BSR = PLS \text{ weight} \div \text{bootstrap SE}$). Chord thickness and darkness scale with BSR, and node size reflects degree across the displayed pairs. Red denotes positive edges, blue negative; nodes are Schaefer 17-network subnetworks. Panel A: higher LV1 scores (representing poor metabolic risk - higher waist, blood pressure, glucose, meat-dominant/Western diet; lower HDL and plant-dominant diet) show mainly between-network links, especially Default to Visual, Default to Somatomotor, and Control to Default, with additional Saliency/Ventral Attention links. Panel B: lower LV1 scores (representing low metabolic risk) show mainly within-network links, especially within Default and within Visual, and fewer Default to Visual links.

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Poster No 53

Brain Age and Morphometry-Cognition Reveal Distinct Patterns in Early- vs. Late-Onset Alzheimer's

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Introduction: Early-onset (EOAD) and Late-onset Alzheimer's Disease (LOAD) may be distinct entities beyond age at onset. By integrating brain age matrices with structural and cognitive analyses, we aimed to identify subtype-specific patterns to improve understanding of AD heterogeneity.

Methods: Structural MRI data of EOAD (n=23) and LOAD (n=192) participants were from the OASIS-4 database. We used brain age matrices (pretrained on Cam-CAN dataset, N=609) and regional analysis of gray matter volume (GMV) and cortical thickness (CT) across 66 bilateral regions. Assessments included 6 standardized cognitive tests (global cognition, executive functions, Logical Memory), GDS behavioral evaluation, and CSF analysis (10 biomarkers: t-tau, p-tau, A β 42, glucose, protein, cell counts). Morphometry-cognition relationships were analyzed via partial correlations (adjusted for age/sex).

Results: EOAD showed significant executive function impairment (TMT-B) and higher brain-PAD scores vs. LOAD. No lobe-level GMV/CT differences were found between groups. Regional CT analysis revealed EOAD-specific patterns in left cingulate gyrus and right parahippocampal gyrus. Morphometry-function relationships differed: In EOAD, TMT-A completion time correlated negatively with temporal/occipital GMV, and GDS weight loss associated with parietal GMV. In LOAD, BNT performance correlated with frontal/occipital/parietal GMV, and limbic GMV associated with verbal fluency. CSF biomarkers showed no between-group differences.

Conclusions: This study demonstrates distinct brain aging patterns and morphometry-cognition relationships between EOAD and LOAD, indicating different underlying mechanisms that may guide patient stratification and interventions.

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Poster No 54

Data-driven Latent Construct Composites of Brain Health are Associated with Cognition and Alzheimer's Disease dementia

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Multimodal composite biomarkers may more holistically capture brain health than individual measures. Here, we seek to validate previously defined composite biomarkers (latent constructs¹) and test their associations with cognition, mild cognitive impairment (MCI) and Alzheimer's disease dementia (AD) in an independent cohort.

We studied 222 PISA² participants (mean age 63, 73% women): 180 healthy controls (HC), 19 MCI and 23 AD. Biomarkers included brain MRI metrics, cardiovascular indices and plasma biomarkers¹. In HCs, confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) defined latent factors. Group differences in factor composite scores were tested with ANCOVA; associations with cognition (Similarities, RAVLT-A, Topographical Test, FAS) with linear regression; and associations of individual measures and composites with MCI/AD diagnosis with logistic regression. Models adjusted for age, sex, intracranial volume and education.

CFA confirmed three factors: Brain & Vascular Health (hippocampal volume, ventricle volume, CBF); WM Fluid Dysregulation (Free Water, WM ePVS); Blood Biomarkers (GFAP, NfL, pTau181). Compared to HCs, MCI and AD had lower Brain & Vascular Health ($F=113.39$, $p<.001$) and higher Blood Biomarkers ($F=94.30$, $p<.001$), with no WM Fluid Dysregulation difference ($F=0.69$, $p=.504$). Brain & Vascular Health related positively, and Blood Biomarkers negatively, to all cognitive tests (all $p>.004$). Brain & Vascular Health showed the strongest association with MCI/AD ($OR=0.07$, $95\%CI=0.03-0.15$), exceeding PET Amyloid Centiloid ($OR=9.94$, $95\%CI=5.27-22.84$).

Biologically meaningful factors were confirmed. Brain & Vascular Health was most strongly associated with MCI/AD. System-level biomarker frameworks may improve early detection and risk stratification in aging and dementia.

1a.

1b.

Figure. Fig 1a. Illustration of factor composites derived from confirmatory factor analysis.

Fig 1b. Individual and composite biomarker associations with MCI/AD dementia

Odds ratios (OR) from logistic regression are shown for each predictor, ranked by magnitude. Values reflect the relative odds of MCI/AD per 1 SD increase in the predictor. Points indicate ORs, and horizontal bars show 95% confidence intervals. For presentation, ORs < 1 were inverted so associations are displayed in the same direction.

Aβ = amyloid-beta; AD = Alzheimer's disease; BG = basal ganglia; BMI = body mass index; CBF = cerebral blood flow; ePVS = enlarged perivascular space volume; fwFA = Free Water-corrected fractional anisotropy; GFAP = glial fibrillary acidic protein; HDL = high-density lipoprotein; MCI = mild cognitive impairment; NfL = neurofilament light chain; PET = positron emission tomography; pTau = phosphorylated tau; WM = white matter.

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Poster No 55

Genetic risk of Alzheimer's and distinct effective connectivity of precuneus during implicit recall

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Neurodegenerative processes accrue over decades before the cognitive symptoms in Alzheimer's Disease (AD), but the nature of these processes is poorly understood. Biomarkers of risk and disease progression may allow intervention before cognitive symptoms emerge. AD pathology encompasses widespread cortical regions, with early involvement of medial temporal, entorhinal and posterior midline regions (Veitch, 2019). Here we explore if neural interactions between these regions change in advance of disease onset by studying people with high genetic risk of AD (Lambert, 2013; Lupton, 2017), who are otherwise healthy and cognitively intact. Given the link between excess amyloid and Alzheimer's, we also tested for altered effective connectivity as a function of amyloid burden (positron emission tomography centiloid score; Bourgeat, 2018). Participants viewed brief news clips, a naturalistic challenge of implicit memory that engages key regions involved in AD, namely the hippocampus, precuneus and angular gyrus.

Mean effective connectivity at the whole-group level related to news viewing was similar to earlier published findings (Ren, 2018), with the effective connectivity from hippocampus to AG being negatively modulated by involuntary memory retrieval (Fig2B). Two effective connections differed in the high-risk group (Fig2C): An increase from AG to precuneus, and a decrease from precuneus to VC. Amyloid burden was associated with increased strength of two backward connections (AG to precuneus and precuneus to VC), an increase in the self-connection of the precuneus (Fig2D), and decreased precuneus to hippocampus connection.

Figure. Upper Panel: A. Implicit recall task included continuing versus naïve conditions of viewing short news stories. For 9 clips, the second half was viewed without seeing the beginning (naïve condition), and for the other 9 clips participants had been shown the first half of the clip 15 minutes earlier. This delayed continuing clip evokes implicit recall of the story introduced in the first half, and is not present for naïve clips given these lack the prior information. B. Participant and group selection Flow Chart; C. General linear model of fMRI data showing wide array of regions with BOLD signal change; top row: task Vs rest; bottom row: continuing Vs naïve conditions.

Lower Panel: C. Dynamic Causal Modelling with Parametric Empirical Bayes (PEB) estimation of group effect of high versus low genetic risk score for Alzheimer's Disease. D. PEB results for association of network parameters with individual participants' amyloid burden (PET-based centiloid scores).

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Poster No 56

Data-Driven Subtyping of Sporadic Frontotemporal Dementia Using Genotype-Specific Longitudinal MRI Trajectories

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Introduction Frontotemporal dementia (FTD) encompasses distinct neuropathologies, with MAPT, GRN, and C9orf72 mutations producing unique neurodegenerative patterns¹. This study tested whether sporadic FTD exhibits comparable longitudinal cortical-thickness trajectories aligned with genetic FTD signatures.

Methods Longitudinal cortical-thickness change was estimated in the ALLFTD cohort using FreeSurfer's longitudinal pipeline, generating Symmetrised Percent Change (SPC) and annualised Rate maps across 68 regions of interest (ROIs). Z-scores were derived from cognitively normal carriers. Genotype-specific trajectories were built from FTD-diagnosed MAPT, GRN, and C9orf72 carriers and used to project sporadic FTD cases into the closest cortical-change template. ROI-wise ANOVAs (FDR<0.05) tested regional differences, and Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA) scores were compared across alignment groups.

Results SPC and Rate analyses showed nearly identical topographies in FTD-diagnosed carriers: MAPT: anterior frontotemporal-insular loss; GRN: posterior frontoparietal-cingulate involvement; C9orf72: diffuse parietal-occipital change. Sporadic projections showed approximately 90% concordance across metrics but low assignment confidence (~35%). Forty-nine ROIs, out of 136 bilateral regions, differed significantly between sporadic subtypes (FDR q<0.05; $\eta^2 = 0.25-0.50$), with spatial patterns closely resembling the carrier genotype topographies. MAPT-aligned cases demonstrated lower MoCA scores (Rate=9.6; SPC=10.9) than GRN (21.25; 21.14) and C9orf72 (20.64; 20.71).

Conclusion Sporadic FTD exhibits cortical and clinical profiles aligning with genotype-derived morphometric axes, suggesting overlapping or transitional forms within a shared continuum of disease progression.

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